

Ancient Pharmacology: Theophrastus' *Historia Plantarum* and Pliny the Elder's *Historia Naturalis*

Scott Alexander Jarmusch

September 14, 2015

MA Ancient History

Dissertation submitted for the Masters degree in Ancient History by Scott Alexander Jarmusch. I certify that (i) any material in this dissertation which is not my own work is properly identified and acknowledged, (ii) the dissertation complies fully with the University of Liverpool regulations on plagiarism and collusion, (iii) no part of the dissertation has ever figured in material successfully submitted for the award of any other degree.

Table Of Contents

<i>HISTORY OF PHARMACOLOGY</i>	Page 3
CHAPTER I. THEOPHRASTUS AND <i>HISTORIA PLANTARUM</i>	Page 16
CHAPTER II. PLINY THE ELDER AND <i>HISTORIA NATURALIS</i>	Page 30
APPENDIX I.	Page 44
BIBLIOGRAPHY	Page 59

HISTORY OF PHARMACOLOGY

The focus of the following study was to examine the state of pharmacology in the ancient world through the texts of Theophrastus and Pliny the Elder to give a better understanding of Classical Greek and Roman pharmacology. Both men authored vital works to the preservation and transmission of pharmacological data. This study will look further into each man's works to evaluate their 'scientific' qualities; how did they conduct their research, how did they write their works, and how each work is vital for the interdisciplinarity of history and science. Each work will also be evaluated for its scientific value today, relating the information each man wrote and how it can be used for current research. Ultimately, this study has the goal of showing that ancient texts have a vital role to play in a larger capacity than just the humanities, but also the sciences.

Science is an evolving being that requires progress and with the inclusion of historic texts, which have been underutilized, there is a whole new body of research to be discovered. Before examining Theophrastus' *Enquiry into Plants* or *Historia Plantarum* and Pliny the Elder's *Natural History* or *Historia Naturalis*, it is useful to examine the history of pharmacology up to their works and briefly examining the impact of their works after ancient times. Pharmacology begins prehistorically with some evidence of early modern humans and the use of plants. The beginning of written history is where the beginnings of pharmacology start to take shape. To better understand the tradition each man was continuing and their impacts on future progress, the brief history of pharmacology will be examined in ancient Mesopotamia, ancient Egypt, Classical Greece, Empirical Rome, The Golden Age of Islam, and the European Renaissance. There is of course a large tradition of pharmacology in Chinese and Indian medicine, but for the study of Theophrastus and Pliny, the pharmacology of the Mediterranean is all that needs to be encompassed.

PREHISTORIC PHARMACOLOGY

Pharmacology begins with the origins of medicine in the ancient world, but plants being used for medicinal purposes dates back into prehistory. When discussing the prehistoric nature of pharmacology, the focus will solely be on human prehistory, naturally. Major G. Seelig described the nature of prehistoric man into three distinctive sections of disease recognition:

“First, the savage man construed the natural as the supernatural-as many of us still do. Rain, storm, thunder, lightening, volcanic eruptions, quakes and tidal waves were to the savage mind indubitable evidence of offended gods, devils, demons or malevolent spirits. Disease was of course the unwelcome omen of the displeasure of these offended forces. Second, he capitalized the idea of sorcery and believed that disease might be induced by a human enemy ‘possessed’ by supernatural powers. Third, he looked upon disease as a result of the intervention of the will of the offended spirits of the dead.”¹

Seelig’s views on early man are a product of examining ‘primitive’ peoples like aboriginal Native Americans, Australian bushmen, and Malayan savages which has been fruitful in terms of looking into prehistoric mans psyche. The nature of man and disease is one that is fundamentally superstitious, and will remain superstitious until Hippocrates divides the two. Since prehistory is quite a mystery in terms of how primitive men lived daily life, burials provide valuable information pharmacologically. One of the earliest examples of the supposed intentional use of plants is the Shanidar IV cave in Iraq; thusly we begin the history of pharmacology here, c. 60,000 B.C.E. Of the numerous grave goods found in the cave, one interesting find was the inclusion of flowers (flower pollen).² The inclusion of flowers in the burial of an important person suggests that the flowers played a certain role in the society, whether it is social or religious. Rightly, there are many theories on the flowers, from it being grave goods to being the collection of ants in the area, but

¹ Seelig, M.G. *Medicine: An Historical Outline*. (Baltimore: The Williams and Wilkins Company, 1931), 5.

² Heinrich, M., Barnes, J., Gibbons, S., Williamson, E. *Fundamentals of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*. (Churchill Livingstone: Elsevier Limited 2003), 10-25.

without written history, this speculative view is the best paleoarchaeologists can infer. The use of plants by early modern humans undoubtedly continued due to *Homo sapiens* inherit reliance on plants, but physical evidence for this is scarce. Therefore, an incomplete record of prehistoric pharmacology exists and will most likely always exist. The next integral evidence for prehistoric use of medicinal plants actually has nothing to do with plants at all, but fungi.

The discovery of Ötzi (1991 C.E.) in the Ötztal Alps, between Austria and Italy, represents the continued evidence of medicinal plant usage in prehistory. Although technically falling within the period of the beginning of written history (c.3400-3200) in Sumer, Ötzi's mummified remains have been traced back to him dying between 3239 and 3105 BCE.³ Ötzi's remains are essential when it comes to medicinal plants or fungi being used regularly. Among the possessions recovered with him included spores of the birch fungus, known to have antibacterial and antimicrobial activity.⁴ Ötzi also had worms at his untimely end, which the birch fungus would have also helped.⁵ Therefore, Ötzi's remains and possessions provide clear evidence for the use of medicinal plants or fungi in prehistoric times. Although the evidence for prehistoric medicinal plant use is miniscule, it still provides key evidence for the continuation of human/plant dependence, an evolutionary trait from *Homo sapiens* earliest primate ancestors. The evolution of pharmacology would take a large step forward with the beginnings of civilization and writing in ancient Mesopotamia.

ANCIENT MESOPOTAMIAN PHARMACOLOGY

The beginnings of written history also provide the beginnings of pharmacy and pharmacology. The information known to physicians, healers, herbalists, shamans, etc., would be written down after centuries of oral transmission to allow

³ Bonani, G. et al. "AMS ¹⁴C Age Determination of Tissue, Bone, and Grass Samples from the Ötztal Ice Man." *Radiocarbon* 36(2), (1994): 247-250.

⁴ Heinrich, *Fundamentals of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 10-25.

⁵ *Ibid.*, 10-25.

for easier diagnoses of patients. JoAnn Scurlock examined the history of pharmacology in Mesopotamia through the vademecum (Pharmacist's companion) texts, the *Šammu šikinšu* ("the nature of plants") and the ancient plant glossary, Uruanna.⁶ She further elaborates on the nature of vademecum texts and how they would have been used:

"Vademecum texts are laid out in a chart format, and give the name of each plant to be discussed, its primary use, and the method of preparation. Organization is by usage. These texts were presumably primarily designed so that the pharmacist presented with a patient with an easily or already diagnosed problem knew what plants needed to be administered. Since the fewer the plants that were employed, the lower the cost, this would allow for the least expensive possible relief for the patient's condition. The physician would also have found this a handy reference work for recommending simple treatments to indigent patients."⁷

Although early in the history of pharmacy and pharmacology, the organization of plant information was vital to the administration of drugs and remedies. The remaining texts, the *Šammu šikinšu* and the Uruanna, represent the more 'scientific' side of Mesopotamian pharmacology. Being similar to many other ancient texts on plants, both contain taxonomic information on plants, different names of the same plants, the primary use of the plant, and the method of preparation.⁸ Further evidence for plant usage in the ancient Mesopotamian, and to be more exact the Sumerian world, comes from Marvin Powell:

"Akkadian *sammu*, "plant/herb," is the word for drug par excellence. And here the great number of these makes it almost impossible to offer a succinct, suggestive summary, except to say that the plants and plant parts used in preparation of drugs extend from common vegetables and trees through grasses and other plants that grew wild

⁶ Scurlock, J. *Sourcebook for Ancient Mesopotamian Medicine*. (Atlanta: SBL Press, 2014), 273.

⁷ *Ibid.*, 273.

⁸ *Ibid.*, 281-289.

in the swamps and hinterlands to a whole array of imported plant products among which the gums and resins are a striking example.”⁹

The underlying problem inherently associated with trying to investigate further back in written history, and in this case, the origins of written history, is that material doesn't survive, both physically and intellectually. “Mesopotamian medical practice has been lost to us as a result of it being transmitted by oral tradition: father to son and master to apprentice, something which characterizes virtually all of the technical professions of antiquity”.¹⁰ Fortunately texts have survived the ancient traditions and have allowed valuable insight into the beginnings of pharmacy and pharmacology.

ANCIENT EGYPTIAN PHARMACOLOGY

Pharmacology in ancient Egypt, much like in Mesopotamia, is widely unknown and vague besides the information gathered from papyri. Dating to around 1700 B.C.E., seven papyrus scrolls that are most likely copies of older texts, contain the principle evidence and knowledge of pharmacology in ancient Egypt.¹¹ The Ebers Papyrus, which contains over 900 specific drugs, has been cross-referenced with “non-medical papyrus, drawings, analogy with function and in a few cases based on identification of remnants in labeled jars. However, the bulk of drugs of vegetable origin in particular remain to be identified.”¹² Drugs were derived from three principle sources: animals, plants, and minerals. Plant material includes domestic and imported species of herbs and plants, “unfortunately of the 160 plant

⁹ Powell, M. “Drug and Pharmaceuticals in Ancient Mesopotamia.” ed. Irene & Walter Jacob. *The Healing Past: Pharmaceuticals in the Biblical and Rabbinic World*. (Leiden: E.J. Brill, 1993), 60.

¹⁰ Ibid., 55.

¹¹ Michael D. Parkins. “Pharmacological Practices of Ancient Egypt.” Presentation at the Proceedings of the 10th Annual History of Medicine Days, University of Calgary, Calgary, AB, Canada, March 23-24, 2001, 5.

¹² Ibid., 6.

products described in the medical Papyruses we have thus far been able to identify only 20%.”¹³ Of those identified, Egyptologists have focused on analgesics:

“There is some evidence that the ancient Egyptians were able to use morphine obtained from opiates. In particular, *shepen* (believed to be the opium poppy) was given to children to stop their crying. This practice has been continued through the ages and used as recently as the mid-nineteenth century in England. The Egyptians used cannabis as a drug and for making hemp ropes. Cannabis (*shemshemet*) was administered by mouth, rectum, vagina, topically, and fumigation, however, there is no evidence that the Egyptians were aware of its psychotropic effects. The mystical lotus flower (*seshen*), described in many papyri and depicted in many drawings is believed to be *Nymphaea spp.* The lotus flower was frequently soaked in beer or wine and the extract drunk. This extract contains four powerful alcohol soluble alkaloids with significant psychotropic effects.”¹⁴

Overall, plant pharmacology in ancient Egypt evolved from a magical nature into one with an early ‘scientific’ base. “That is to say that drugs used in the specific therapies were first chosen based on perceived magical potential, and those that were continued were chosen based on empirical observation. The *swnw* [physicians] lacked the information regarding internal disorders and their causes that we possess today. Rather, their therapies were based on a misconstrued physiologic theory and empirical observation.”¹⁵ Even though many remedies for ancient diseases deriving from plant materials did not provide any cure or relief, the remedies described in papyri do contain activity. “Of the 260 prescriptions in the Hearst Papyrus, 28 percent contain an ingredient which can be perceived to have had activity towards the condition being treated. Another third of these remedies supplied to any given disorder would produce a purgative effect on the gastrointestinal system”.¹⁶ The developments in medicine and pharmacology in ancient Egypt allowed for the integration of useful deductions regarding medicinal

¹³ Ibid., 8.

¹⁴ Ibid., 8.

¹⁵ Ibid., 11.

¹⁶ Ibid., 11.

plants. This development would evolve more greatly in Classical Greece under the guidance of great philosophers.

CLASSICAL GREEK PHARMACOLOGY

The writers of Classical Greek pharmacology are three giants: Hippocrates, Aristotle, and Theophrastus. Beginning with Hippocrates, the “father of western medicine”, he included over 400 plants that he used in practice.¹⁷ Although not specifically interested in cataloguing the plants and information about them, Hippocrates certainly took advantage of the wealth of knowledge inherited from previous traditions. “Many of these were poisonous, including ‘Absinthe (Wormwood), anemone, byrony, hellebore, hemlock, henbane, ivy, mandragora (mandrake), poppy, squills, etc.’”¹⁸ Hippocrates’ fascination with medicine did not allow for the progression of pharmacology that Theophrastus’ works would embark upon, but Theophrastus’ work with pharmacology will be examined in greater detail in chapter I. From Hippocrates, Aristotle brought about the next change in pharmacology, though not directly influencing the overall knowledge of the field.

Aristotle’s key work the *History of Animals* established a systemized classification of animals. Through his works on animals, Aristotle taught his student and friend Theophrastus how to morphologically classify different species. This system allowed Theophrastus to write his influential works on botany. There is a good chance that both were influenced first by the works of Plato, and that Aristotle adapted Plato’s teachings into his own.¹⁹ Without the influence of Aristotle and the way to classify species based on differences, botany and pharmacology had no way of advancing past its archaic roots. This is directly seen in the way Theophrastus uses Aristotle’s taxonomy in *Historia Plantarum* and *De Causis Plantarum*.

¹⁷ Bevan-Jones, R. *Poisonous Plants: A Cultural and Social History*. (Oxford: Windgather Press, 2009), Pt. 1.

¹⁸ *Ibid.* Pt.1.

¹⁹ Scarborough, John. “Drugs and Drug Lore in the Time of Theophrastus: Folklore, Magic, Botany, Philosophy, and the Rootcutters”. *Acta* 49, (2006): 5.

Interestingly enough, no great schedule of drugs is known to exist from this era.²⁰ Theophrastus creates the closest thing to this, who will again be discussed in greater detail in chapter I.

ANCIENT ROMAN PHARMACOLOGY

Similar to Classical Greece, Rome too had three giants of pharmacology: Dioscorides, Pliny the Elder, and Galen. The Roman army physician Dioscorides in his work *De Materia Medica* (65 A.D.) wrote solely on the “definition and function of spices” and “the contribution of spices to pharmacology”, which is essential for the study of pharmacology through the Renaissance²¹, mentioning nearly 600 species of plants.²² Dioscorides was essential in furthering the general knowledge of medicinal herbs and spices in the classical world, including those being introduced from the East.²³ Dioscorides’ works survived well due to the fact that Arabic scientists and physicians used his work as their principle source, maybe due to the fact that it was translated into multiple languages multiple times.²⁴ The importance the Medieval Arabic world played on pharmacology will be touched upon later.

In order to better understand the way drugs were chosen in the Greek and Roman period, Plinio Prioreshi in *A History of Medicine: Vol. III - Roman Medicine*, outlines the combinatorial understanding of how plants were determined to have pharmacological properties in the ancient world:

“(1) There were plants that, when ingested, produced some obvious effects (e.g., hellebore caused vomiting, and certain mushrooms, sickness and death). (2) Others were declared effective according to the principle that if there is a similarity (fanciful or real) between an

²⁰ Weatherall, M. “Drug Treatment and Rise of Pharmacology.” In *The Cambridge History of Medicine*, ed. Roy Porter. (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2006), 212.

²¹ Heinrich, *Fundamentals of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 10-25.

²² Scarborough, J. “Early Byzantine Pharmacology.” *Dumbarton Oaks Papers Symposium on Byzantine Medicine*, 38 (1984), 215.

²³ *Ibid.*, 213-215.

²⁴ Levey, M. *Early Arabic Pharmacology: An Introduction*, 25.

agent (or part of it, for example, the fruit of a plant) and an organ of the body or symptom of a disease, such an agent would be beneficial for that organ or symptom. For example, the plant orchis, which had a root resembling two human testicles, was believed to relieve various diseases of the genitals and to affect libido. This principle, later called the “Doctrine of the Signatures,” was in essence the concept of *similia similibus curantur* (“like cures like”), which went back to Hippocratic pharmacology. (3) Drugs were often deemed to have “qualities” attributed to them for reasons that had little relation with reality. As diseases also had “qualities”, they were often treated with drugs that possessed opposite qualities...Thus, epilepsy, being cold and moist, would be treated with heating and drying substances. (4) Still, others may have been declared effective because they were bitter, strong, or generally unpleasant to the taste. Pliny said, for example, that a certain plant is “harsh to the taste and therefore good of the fluxion of the eyes”. (5) Plants originally used in prayers and magic rituals may eventually have been considered therapeutically useful.”²⁵

From these steps to determine the activity of a plant, it is evident that the evolution from superstition to empirical observations is not complete. Since superstition still played a imperative role in the daily lives of ancient peoples, they still hold valuable weight to society. Therefore the mixing of superstition, magic, and empirical observations builds the foundation for Greek and Roman pharmacology.

A contemporary to Dioscorides, Pliny the Elder created the most extensive encyclopedia known from the ancient world, with remedies from plants and animals contributing twelve of the thirty-seven books compiled. Pliny’s contributions to pharmacology will be one of the main focuses of this study as well, so therefore, *Historia Naturalis* will be bypassed for the time being, and the contributions of Galen will be the next focus of Roman pharmacology.

Galen was like Hippocrates in the fact that he was a physician interested in the human anatomy. Galen too saw the importance drugs from plants played in the treatment of humans. Some argue that it is Galen’s works that acted as the foundation which Arabic authors built their pharmacological knowledge upon.²⁶ It comes as no surprise that Galen’s works on pharmacology and pharmacy are

²⁵ Prioreschi, P., *A History of Medicine: Vol. III - Roman Medicine* (Omaha: Horatius Press, 1998), 730.

²⁶ Levey, M. *Early Arabic Pharmacology: An Introduction*, 101.

dispersed among many treatises: “Mixtures and Properties of Simples, Compound Drugs Arranged by Location of Ailment, Compound Drugs Arranged by Kind, Antidotes, and similar tracts”.²⁷ Galen’s influences can be seen in the works of Dioscorides and all of the famous simples known from the time of Theophrastus.²⁸ Between the works of Dioscorides, Pliny the Elder, and Galen, the advancement of pharmacology up until the Middle Ages is unknown. It is not until the great scientists, physicians, and authors of the Islamic world that pharmacological knowledge leap ahead again.

PHARMACOLOGY IN THE ISLAMIC-ARABIC GOLDEN AGE

The Islamic-Arabic Golden Age (~750 – 1258 C.E.) marked an unprecedented leap in the biological sciences, building on the previous works from Egypt, Persia, Greece, Rome, etc.²⁹ One of the most significant factors leading to the advancement of scientific knowledge in this period can be traced to the innumerable amount of translations from Greek, Latin, and Chinese. The removal of the language barrier, plus the influences of the Quran on agnostic learning and the establishment of The House of Wisdom in Baghdad in 1004 CE³⁰, allowed for the rate of scientific progress to reach an all-time high, not seen again until the Renaissance and the Enlightenment. This “Golden Age” is where the works of Dioscorides and Galen become highly influential.

As the most fact-based science of the Arabic period, Pharmacology specifically saw an unprecedented advancement, with the knowledge of this age lasting until the nineteenth century.³¹ The writings of Dioscorides appear in the Arabic record due to the translations made by early scholars around the ninth

²⁷ Scarborough, “Early Byzantine Pharmacology”, 216.

²⁸ Ibid., 216.

²⁹ Falagas, M. et al. “Arab science in the golden age (750-1258 C.E.) and today”. *FASEB* 20, (2006): 1581.

³⁰ Ibid., 1582.

³¹ Levey, M. *Early Arabic Pharmacology: An Introduction*, Preface.

century CE.³² “It was Iṣṭafān ibn Basīl who first translated Dioscorides’ *Materia Medica* into Arabic; it was done without an intermediate Syriac translation. Iṣṭafān, a resident of Baghdad, was a pupil of famed Ḥunain ibn Ishāq who later retranslated and improved much of the work.”³³ The “Simple Drugs” of Galen was translated in the early ninth century by Yāsuf al-Khūrī, Ayyūb, and Ḥunain ibn Ishāq.³⁴ The reliance on Dioscorides and Galen in this period is essential to understanding the ability to advance the science of pharmacology:

“ Not only was the *Materia Medica* of Dioscorides used as a base by many Muslim writers but, because of its flexibility of arrangement for further study and research, in the hands of the Arabs it led to a greater improvement in pharmacology. The Dioscorides treatise overcame the rigidity of the earlier Mesopotamian lexical lists.

Considered on the scale of its value for individual physicians of early Arabic times, the Dioscorides text provided a ready reference to most simples, especially of the Mediterranean area, their synonyms, provenience, description of morphological parts used, appearance, preparation, and pharmacological data.”³⁵

Furthering the knowledge Dioscorides provided that Arab world, Ibn al-Baytar wrote the alphabetical guide *The Comprehensive Book on Materia Medica and Foodstuffs*, containing over 1400 simples.³⁶ “Arab scholars became acquainted with herbs, experimented with anesthetics, developed techniques such as distillation, crystallization, solution, and calcinations and introduced new drugs such as camphor, senna, musk, alum, sandalwood, ambergris, mercury, aloes, and aconite. They also developed syrups and juleps, created flavoring extracts made of rose water, orange or lemon peel, and experimented with poisons and antidotes.”³⁷ Before the invasions of the Crusades and the Mongols and the subsequent destruction of the Arab world, the intellectual activities of Arab scholars were

³² Ibid., 26.

³³ Ibid., 26.

³⁴ Ibid., 101.

³⁵ Ibid., 25.

³⁶ Falagas, “Arab science in the golden age (750-1258 C.E.) and today”, 1584.

³⁷ Ibid., 1584.

unrivalled.³⁸ “While the Muslim world enjoyed this ‘Golden Age’, Europe was still going through its ‘Dark Ages’. Many advances in science and technology of the Islamic civilization later provided the impetus for the development of the European Renaissance.”³⁹ Only with the fall of Cordoba and Baghdad in the thirteenth century C.E. did this astounding progress halt.

RENAISSANCE PHARMACOLOGY

There are several factors that played to the rapid advancement of medicine and pharmacology in the Renaissance including the printing press and the Reformation. With these two events occurring, herbalists from every country were gathering plants and gathering knowledge to treat disease. The advances in pharmacology came from Valerius Cordus and the expanding of Dioscorides’ work. This “marked the transition from magic, spells, and alchemy to a rational approach to chemical experimentation.”⁴⁰ This “recovery in the fifteenth century of the works of Dioscorides and Theophrastus prepared the way for a renewal in pharmacy.”⁴¹ Also the standardization of drug preparation from Vesalius ensured uniformity in drug dosages.⁴² In addition to *De Materia Medica* still being utilized, the excitement of the New World added new prospects for chemical therapeutics.⁴³ Maybe the most influential figure in Renaissance pharmacology and medicine is Paracelsus.

Paracelsus represents the first change in thinking against the ancient thoughts of pharmacology, as he consistently challenges the ideas of Hippocrates and Galen. It is Galenic pharmacology that he called a “foreign system, grown in

³⁸ Cooper, W. *Challenges of the Muslim World: Present, Future and Past*. (UK: Emerald Group Publishing Limited, 2008), 215.

³⁹ *Ibid.*, 215.

⁴⁰ Hacker, M., Messer II, W., Bachmann, K. *Pharmacology: Principles and Practice*. (USA: Elsevier, 2009), 4.

⁴¹ Ed. Wear, A., French, R.K., Lonie, I.M. *The Medical Renaissance of the Sixteenth Century*. (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1985), 101.

⁴² Hacker, M., Messer II, W., Bachmann, K. *Pharmacology: Principles and Practice*. (USA: Elsevier, 2009), 4.

⁴³ Ed. Wear, A., French, R.K., Lonie, I.M. *The Medical Renaissance of the Sixteenth Century*. (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1985), 100.

Greece and Arabia and used in modern times and other countries”.⁴⁴ It is truly Paracelsus advances in chemistry and the scientific method that his legacy in pharmacology was cemented. Many have argued that Paracelsus’ progress is merely grounded in the works of his predecessors, but “it was Paracelsus himself who prepared the ground for modern medicinal chemistry by his unorthodox methods, by his stimulating reformatory and revolutionising attitude and in spite of his blending of philosophical, religious and Naturalistic ideas.”⁴⁵ From this point onward, pharmacology developed along with the other sciences until the great leaps forward in the nineteenth and twentieth centuries.

After the European Renaissance, the works of Dioscorides, Theophrastus, and Galen become slowly phased out as more modern authors surpassed their scientifically outdated works. With the Age of Enlightenment opening the door for science and the subsequent advances in technology around the Industrial Revolution, modern pharmacologists and chemists began the rapid evolution of science that has persisted and prevailed until the twenty-first century.

⁴⁴ Pagel, W. *Paracelsus: An Introduction to Philosophical Medicine in the Era of the Renaissance*. (Basel: S.Karger AG, 1982), 243.

⁴⁵ *Ibid.*, 273.

CHAPTER I. THEOPHRASTUS AND *HISTORIA PLANTARUM*

INTRODUCTION

Originating from the ancient Greek *pharmakon* meaning 'poison', pharmacology grew under the guidance of Theophrastus (371-287 BCE). Working from Hippocrates' material, Theophrastus altered the working knowledge of plants that transcended the Middle Ages and through the Renaissance. His two botanical works, *De Causis Plantarum* (On the Causes of Plants) and *Historia Plantarum* (Enquiry into Plants), "formed the base for all succeeding studies of plant lore and classification until the Linnaean system."⁴⁶ Although Theophrastus' works cover many scientific and academic fields, his works on botany have proven the most resonate throughout pharmacology and botanical history, unfortunately due to the fact that they are some of the few that survive.

The majority of biographical information detailing Theophrastus' life is derived from Diogenes Laertius' *Lives of Eminent Philosophers*, written sometime between the 2nd and 5th centuries C.E. As the seminal work considered the history of Greek philosophy throughout the Middle Ages, as seen through Walter Burley's *De vita et moribus philosophorum*, Diogenes' *Lives* has become less relevant in modern times due to lack of sources and reliability on the author's part.⁴⁷ Herbert S. Long said, "In any given passage he is as useful and reliable as the source he happens to be quoting at that exact moment."⁴⁸ Regardless of the pitfalls of Diogenes' work, it remains a irreplaceable source on Theophrastus' life and works.

Theophrastus was born on the island of Lesbos, at Eresos, and was sent to Athens to study under the guidance of Plato. Diogenes exalts, "Theophrastus was a man of remarkable intelligence and industry. Furthermore, he was ever ready to do

⁴⁶ Scarborough, J., "Theophrastus on Herbals and Herbal Remedies," *Journal of the History of Biology* 11, (1978): 353.

⁴⁷ Diogenes Laertius, *Lives of Eminent Philosophers*, Introduction, xix. Translation by R.D. Hicks, The Loeb Classical Library. (Cambridge, The Harvard University Press, 1972).

⁴⁸ *Ibid.*, Introduction, xix.

a kindness and fond of discussion".⁴⁹ Diogenes goes on to note an anecdote on Theophrastus' value in Athens in which Agnonides aimed to prosecute Theophrastus for impiety, but narrowly escaped punishment himself.⁵⁰ Sir Arthur Hort mentions in his translation of Theophrastus' *Enquiry into Plants* that it is from Plato that Theophrastus learns the importance of classification, and not from Aristotle. John Scarborough agrees with Hort, "One cannot understand Aristotelian biology, or the zoology and botany of Theophrastus without taking into account of Plato's heavy authority."⁵¹ Regardless of who taught Theophrastus the basics of classification, he broke away from his predecessors and focused on the plants of the Mediterranean and exotic lands.⁵²

Theophrastus' knowledge benefited from the campaigns of Philip and Alexander of Macedon. Theophrastus used this knowledge brought back from trained observers to describe the flora of the exotic lands east of Greece, like pepper, cinnamon, frankincense, and myrrh.⁵³ According to Diogenes, Theophrastus had 2000 pupils attend his lectures and Sir Alfred Hort postulated in his translation, "May we not hazard a guess that a number of the students were appropriately employed in the collection of facts and observations?"⁵⁴ Furthermore, he goes on to explain his reasoning:

"The assumption that a number of 'travelling students' were so employed would at all events explain certain references in Theophrastus' botanical works. He says constantly 'The Macedonians say,' 'The men of Mount Ida say' and so forth. Now it seems hardly improbable that he is quoting from written treatises by Macedonians or Idaean writers. It is at least a plausible suggestion that in such references he is referring to reports of the districts in question contributed by the students of the school. In that case 'The

⁴⁹ Ibid., V, 483.

⁵⁰ Ibid., V, 483.

⁵¹ Scarborough, J., "Drugs and Drug Lore in the Time of Theophrastus: Folklore, Magic, Botany, Philosophy, and the Rootcutters," *Acta* 49, (2006): 5.

⁵² Theophrastus, *Enquiry into Plants*, Introduction, xvii. Translation by Sir Arthur Hort, The Loeb Classical Library. (Cambridge, The Harvard University Press, 1946).

⁵³ Ibid., Introduction, xix-xx.

⁵⁴ Ibid., Introduction, xx.

Macedonians say' would mean 'This is what our representative was told in Macedonia.' It is further noticeable that the tense used is sometimes past, *e.g.* 'The men of Mount Ida *said*'; an obvious explanation of this is supplied by the above conjecture. It is even possible that in one place (3. 12. 4.) the name of one of these students has been preserved."⁵⁵

Despite being underneath Aristotle after the death of Plato, Hort mentions that instead of being teacher and student, Aristotle and Theophrastus were more peers and mainly friends.⁵⁶ It was Aristotle in fact that gave Theophrastus his moniker.⁵⁷ Aristotle left the position of Lyceum head and its' gardens to Theophrastus in 322 after his death,⁵⁸ no doubt leading to many of the botanical observations found in Theophrastus' works. In 307/6, Sophocles of Sunium introduced a law that no philosopher could be at the head of a school except with Senatorial permission and popular opinion.⁵⁹ Theophrastus left Athens but was vindicated one year later, when Philon prosecuted Sophocles for making an illegal proposal.⁶⁰

Theophrastus lived to the age of 85 and over his long life he amassed an astonishing variety of works that Diogenes regarded as "excellence of every kind".⁶¹ Ranging from a myriad of topics including animals (no doubt a continuation of Aristotle's works), sickness and diseases, love, politics, physics, the soul, the ludicrous, music, laws, etc. In all, Diogenes recognizes 232,808 lines of which Theophrastus authored.⁶² Unfortunately, the majority of Theophrastus' works haven't survived, but Theophrastus' works on plants, specifically *Historia Plantarum* and *De Causis Plantarum*, have survived due to Romans like Dioscorides, Pliny the

⁵⁵ Ibid., Introduction, xx-xxi.

⁵⁶ Ibid., Introduction, xviii.

⁵⁷ Diogenes, *Lives*, V, 485.

⁵⁸ Ibid., V, 487.

⁵⁹ Diogenes, *Lives*, V, 485; O'Sullivan, Lara. "The Law of Sophocles and the Beginnings of Permanent Philosophical Schools in Athens". *Testimonia Homerica* 145, (2002): 251-262.

⁶⁰ Diogenes, *Lives*, V, 485

⁶¹ Ibid., V, 489

⁶² Ibid., V, 489-503

Elder, Galen, and furthermore Arabic scholars who had learned Greek from the early 1st millennium C.E.⁶³

STRUCTURE & STYLE

Theophrastus' works on plants are parts of a larger grouping of lectures *On Odours*, which he most likely worked on until his death. Einarson defines that his works are not a 'textbook', but are actually more like research journals.⁶⁴ *Historia Plantarum* classifies and identifies plants from gathered information via morphology whereas *De Causis Plantarum* explains the common or distinctive characteristics of plants. These works are definitively the "first fundamental ordering of botany (pot-herbs, wild species, some trees, vines, many other 'classes' of plants) by means of morphology, as well as a description of those plants considered foods, drugs, and other species which had special powers or properties that were portions of a very ancient folklore."⁶⁵ The contents of these two works are derived directly from Aristotle's *History of Animals*, which classifies animals from gathered information, and Aristotle's later works on animals (*On the parts of Animals*, *On the Generation of Animals*, *On the Motion of Animals*, *On the Soul*, and *Parva Naturalia*) explaining common or distinctive traits.⁶⁶ Theophrastus' challenge was easier than Aristotle's though Scarborough states:

"Plant nomenclature is slightly more assured. A multitude of names was applied to poisonous snakes, for example, while plant names in Theophrastus, Nicander, Dioscorides, Galen, and others have some consistency that helps in modern identification. Specific plants had names recognized throughout the Greek world, and where there is doubt, Modern Greek sometimes preserves an essential word or core that helps key modern nomenclature. Once a plant is keyed, one may determine through modern biochemistry and pharmacology if the

⁶³ Egerton, Frank N., *History of plant science*. (Ipswich: Salem Press Encyclopedia of Science, 2015), online.

⁶⁴ Theophrastus, *De Causis Plantarum*, Introduction, ix. Translation by Benedict Einarson and George K.K. Link, The Loeb Classical Library. (Cambridge: The Harvard University Press, 1976).

⁶⁵ Scarborough, "Drugs and Drug Lore," 1.

⁶⁶ Theophrastus, *De Causis Plantarum*, Introduction, ix.

substance had beneficial or harmful effects. Quite often, empirical observation as recorded by Theophrastus or Diocles is correct, although the manner of description fits the Peripatetic mold.”⁶⁷

John Scarborough pronounces, “Taking Aristotle’s methodologies, illustrated in the *Historia Animalium*, *De Partibus Animalium*, and other zoological works, Theophrastus produced a botanical guide that displayed the best in the Peripatetic approaches of the world of nature.”⁶⁸ Theophrastus categorized plants based on habitat firstly, so ‘terrestrial’ and ‘aquatic’. He then further categorized plants based on morphology, which he divided into ‘kinds’ and ‘differences’.⁶⁹ Theophrastus’ accomplishment in categorizing more than 550 plant species is quite astonishing, especially without the standardized methodology of modern biology. Taxonomy is an old phenomenon, tracing back further through ancient history, back to the ancient Egyptian’s papyri.⁷⁰ Not until the mid-seventeenth century and Carl Linnaeus’ binomial naming system did taxonomy become a standardized science, something both Aristotle and Theophrastus would have benefited from immensely.

Theophrastus strictly cites his sources throughout both *Historia Plantarum* and *De Causis Plantarum*. Einarson mentions, “Aristotle is the most prominent, and is often corrected, although never mentioned by name. Where Aristotle fails him, Theophrastus resorts to Plato.”⁷¹ Theophrastus also cites Democritus, Empedocles, and Anaxagoras in descending order of frequency. Contemporary sources were never mentioned by name, as was good practice for authors, as seen by Theophrastus close correspondence Phantias of Eresus.⁷² Theophrastus was chiefly interested in collecting information not known to writers on agriculture. His sources on foreign plants, wild trees, and aquatic and marine plants were the woodcutters of

⁶⁷ Scarborough, “Theophrastus on Herbals and Herbal Remedies”, 357-358.

⁶⁸ *Ibid.*, 353.

⁶⁹ Theophrastus, *De Causis Plantarum*, Introduction, xvii.; Scarborough, “Drugs and Drug Lore”, 1.

⁷⁰ Michael D. Parkins. “Pharmacological Practices of Ancient Egypt.” Presentation at the Proceedings of the 10th Annual History of Medicine Days, University of Calgary, Calgary, AB, Canada, March 23-24, 2001, 5.

⁷¹ Theophrastus, *De Causis Plantarum*, Introduction, xix.

⁷² *Ibid.*, Introduction, xx.

Arcadia, Mt. Ida and Macedonia.⁷³ He also procured information from the “*pharmacopōlai* (“drug-vendors”) and *rhizotomoi* [“root-cutters”]” that were active in the *agorai* in the Greek cities from Sicily through the eastern Mediterranean.⁷⁴ This Scarborough says is the defining feature of Theophrastus’ works that divides himself apart from Aristotle. “Aristotle knew such professionals throughout his life, but it was Theophrastus who took them as primary sources of what he concluded about pharmacologically-active plants as contrasted to the botanical lore that encompassed only nutrition.”⁷⁵

The authenticity of Book IX in *Historia Plantarum* has been brought into question due to the topics in Book IX, which historians have argued deviate from the remainder of the treatise covered.⁷⁶ Scarborough dismissed these worries:

“Whatever one may believe about the authenticity of Book IX of the *Historia Plantarum*, there is ample evidence in the rest of the work, and in *De Causis Plantarum*, that attests to Theophrastus’s great interest in medicinals, and plant medicinals in particular. Omitting *Historia Plantarum* IX from consideration of the Theophrastean *corpus* does grave injustice to the history of ancient botany and ancient pharmacy: here are medicinals, derived from plants – and one animal.”⁷⁷

Another cause of questioning the creditability of Theophrastus is his fascination with magical accounts.

Theophrastus explicitly states that he is interested in the “things that are called fairy tales by earlier thinkers” due to the empirical information contained within the tales.⁷⁸ Theophrastus cites that the druggists and herb-diggers say when “cutting some roots one should stand to windward, - for instance, in cutting *thapsia* among others, and that one should first anoint oneself with oil, for that one’s will

⁷³ Ibid., Introduction, xx.

⁷⁴ Scarborough, “Theophrastus on Herbals and Herbal Remedies”, 356; Scarborough, “Drugs and Drug Lore”, 11.

⁷⁵ Scarborough, “Drugs and Drug Lore”, 11.

⁷⁶ Ibid., 353.

⁷⁷ Ibid., 354.

⁷⁸ Scarborough, “Drugs and Drug Lore”, 11.

swell up if one stands the other way.”⁷⁹ This information is useful to Theophrastus as it gives valuable information to the plants nature and reveals special features of plants. The superstitious side of *rhizotomoi* results from a long held beliefs, beliefs that Theophrastus doesn’t claim as absurdities, but simply the way *rhizotomoi* operated. “All this ‘practical-stuff’: Theophrastus carefully distinguishes the useful, the relevant, and the productive from those customs and procedures that were merely ‘tradition,’ or which were parts of true superstitions, well-known from medico-pharmaceutical rites performed by the stereotypical talismanic-obsessed man in his *Characters*.”⁸⁰ Therefore, Theophrastus combined both the practical knowledge morphology provided him and blended this information with teleological information gathered from folklore and *rhizotomoi*.

Stylistically, Theophrastus was unmatched in the ‘divinity’ of his works. Therefore, Aristotle dubbed him the moniker Theophrastus, or ‘indicated by a god’.⁸¹ Einarson gives a detailed understanding of Theophrastus’ divine writing:

“Theophrastus writes the *Kunstprosa* or euphonic prose of the day, such as we see in the *Constitution of Athens*. Such prose endeavours to borrow the graces of poetry without ceasing to be prose. It remains prose by avoiding all poetical or non-current words and all oddities of syntax or idiom, and it seeks to please the ear by avoiding hiatus and having a certain rhythm and balanced structure of its own.”⁸²

Without the metered restrictions, “*Kunstprosa* is characterized by the use of figures of speech, ‘poetic coloration,’ and rhythm. This denoted a style of composition first established in the late sixth century B.C.E. by some of the early philosophers, including Gorgias, Democritus, Heraclitus, and Thrasymachus.”⁸³ Victor Bers mentions the “prestige of literary traditions” allowed for the transmission of *Kunstprosa* through the Renaissance in the vernacular languages of writers, but, unfortunately there must have been “beautiful, non-metrical speech” that had gone

⁷⁹ Theophrastus, *Historia Plantarum*, IX, 257.

⁸⁰ Scarborough, “Drugs and Drug Lore”, 12-13.

⁸¹ Theophrastus, *De Causis Plantarum*, Introduction, xxiii.

⁸² *Ibid.*, Introduction, xxix.

⁸³ Bers, V., “*Kunstprosa*: Philosophy, History, Oratory,” In *Companion to the Ancient Greek Language*. ed. Bakker, E.J. (Hoboken: Wiley-Blackwell, 2010), 455.

unrecorded.⁸⁴ When Theophrastus' works are more closely examined, there is an obvious relationship to the philosophers whom preceded him; from the similarities in structure to Aristotle's *History on Animals* to the writing style derived from men like Plato, which was "between poetry and prose" according to Aristotle.⁸⁵ Although not strictly mentioned in Bers chapter in *Companion to the Ancient Greek Language*, Theophrastus fits well under the classification of *Kunstprosa* that is associated with the oratory tradition best produced under Isocrates and Demosthenes in the fourth century B.C.E. Theophrastus avoidance of hiatus⁸⁶ matches up well with Isocrates⁸⁷ and considering the audience of Theophrastus' works and the genius Theophrastus exuded, it makes sense he would have tailored his lectures in a style spoken aloud since he was considered an attractive and lively lecturer.⁸⁸

HISTORIA PLANTARUM (ENQUIRY INTO PLANTS)

Theophrastus' *Historia Plantarum* is divided into two volumes including the minor works *On Odours* and *Weather Signs*. Although volume II is of greater interest in this study due to the inclusion of Book IX "Of the Juices of Plants, and of the Medicinal Properties of Herbs", volume I contains valuable information on the criteria for plant classification. The medicinal remedies and properties contained within Theophrastus' work are directly relevant to the study and history of pharmacology. Nevertheless, the information on plant classification directly affects the overall goal of this study. By examining Theophrastus' thought and research processes through his research 'notebook', the practices of ancient science and ancient pharmacology become more apparent. In regards to this, beginning with the first volume of *Historia Plantarum* is essential for the establishment of a comprehensive study.

⁸⁴ Ibid., 455

⁸⁵ Ibid., 463

⁸⁶ Theophrastus, *De Causis Plantarum*, Introduction, xxxi.

⁸⁷ Bers, "Kunstprosa: Philosophy, History, Oratory," 466.

⁸⁸ Theophrastus, *Enquiry into Plants*, Introduction, xxii.

Theophrastus defines the distinctive characteristics of plants and their nature into four categories: “their parts, their qualities, the ways in which their life originates, and the course which it follows in each case”.⁸⁹ Furthermore, Theophrastus defines the problematic nature of working on plant classification by ‘parts’:

“Now it appears that by a ‘part,’ seeing that it is something which belongs to the plant’s characteristic nature, we mean something which is permanent either absolutely or when once it has appeared (like those parts of animals which remain for a time undeveloped) permanent, that is, unless it be lost by disease, age or mutilation. However some of the parts of plants are such that their existence is limited to a year, for instance, flower, ‘catkin,’ leaf, fruit, in fact all those parts which are antecedent to the fruit or else appear along with it. Also the new shoot itself must be include with these; for trees always make fresh growth every year alike in the parts above ground and in those which pertain to the roots. So that is one sets these down as ‘parts,’ the number of parts will be indeterminable and constantly changing; if on the other hand these are not to be called ‘parts,’ the result will be that things which are essential if the plant is to reach its perfection, and which are its conspicuous features, are nevertheless not ‘parts’; for any plant always appears to be, as indeed it is, more comely and more perfect when it makes new growth, blooms, and bears fruit. Such, we may say, are the difficulties involved in defining a ‘part.’”⁹⁰

Theophrastus had to define the way he was classifying plants. In pre-Linnaean terms, Theophrastus relied on Aristotle and Plato for the basics for classification. What makes Theophrastus’ works still relevant today is the fact that he practiced his art in the most standardized fashion of his era and he clearly lays down his definitions for classification in the beginning of the text:

“Now the differences in regard to parts, to take a general view, are of three kinds: either one plant may possess them and another not (for instance, leaves and fruit), or in one plant they may be unlike in appearance or size to those of another, or, thirdly, they may be differently arranged. Now the unlikeness between them is seen in form, colour, closeness of arrangement or its opposite, roughness or

⁸⁹ Ibid., I, 3.

⁹⁰ Ibid., I, 5.

its opposite, and the other qualities; and again there are the various differences of flavor... But, before we attempt to speak about each, we must make a list of the parts themselves. Now the primary and most important parts, which are also common to most, are these-root, stem, branch, twig; these are the parts into which we might divide the plant, regarding them as members, [*i.e.* if we wished to make an anatomical division.] corresponding to members of animals: for each of these is distinct in character from the rest, and together they make up the whole.”⁹¹

Theophrastus then continues with his classification criteria by defining the main part’s essential functions.⁹² The remainder of Book I handles the many differences each ‘kind’ has and how to classify according to these differences. Theophrastus brings the whole of differences between parts to a close with more far-reaching defining features:

“But there appear to be the following differences which affect the plant’s whole being: some are cultivated, some wild; some fruitful, some barren; some evergreen; some deciduous, as was said, while some again have no leaves at all; some are flowing plants, some flowerless; some are early, some late in producing their shoots and fruits; and there are other differences similar to these. Now I may be said that such differences are seen in the parts, or at least that particular parts are concerned in them. But the special, and in a way the most important distinction is one which may be seen in animals too, namely, that some are of the water, some of the land. For of plants too there is a class which cannot grow except in moisture, while others will indeed grow on dry land, but they lose their character and are inferior.”⁹³

As a whole, Book I allows for the reader to gain an insight into Theophrastus’ classification criteria as well as his research methodology. When considering the nature of the work, a research notebook intended for lecturing, it becomes clear that Theophrastus is writing down the process of his classification for future scientists. This is a salient feature in modern science. The step-by-step process of modern experiments is written in fine detail in order to make results reproducible, an

⁹¹ *Ibid.*, I, 9-13.

⁹² *Ibid.*, I, 13-19.

⁹³ *Ibid.* I, 99-101.

essential part of examining the authenticity of an experiment. No doubt learning from his predecessors, Theophrastus had established a process for the identification and classification of plants, although not without ambiguity. Without the ability to rapidly communicate and disseminate his work to other botanists, Theophrastus' works were only available to the people in close proximity or those who had access to his texts like Dioscorides, Pliny the Elder, and Galen.⁹⁴ Book IX on the medicinal properties of herbs contains the information that the Roman authors cite in their works and it is one of the principle texts for pharmacology, besides Pliny the Elder's *Historia Naturalis*, that will be examined in closer detail for this study.

"Moisture belongs to plants as such and some call it the 'sap,' to give it a general name; and it plainly has special qualities in each plant."⁹⁵ The special qualities that Theophrastus is mentioning here include color, taste, smell, viscosity, etc. Later in Book IX, he gives a general account on the medicinal properties of juices and other 'kinds':

"Now we must endeavor to speak in like manner of those juices which have not been mentioned already, I mean, such as are medicinal or have other properties; and at the same time we must speak of root; for some of the juices are derived from roots, and apart from that roots have in themselves divers properties of all kinds; and in general we must discuss medicinal things of all kinds, as fruit, extracted juice, leaves, roots, 'herbs'; for the herb-diggers call some medicinal things by this name."⁹⁶

The variety of plant sources to obtain the medicinal properties is indicative of the nature of ancient science. Science is still an art of trial and error even with the most advanced instrumentation of today. One essential principle of science is that you must have a dependent variable and an independent variable.

The dependent variable changes from experiment to experiment based on several factors and the independent variable shouldn't change not matter what changes in the experiment. This too is the way ancient science operated even

⁹⁴ Scarborough, J. "Early Byzantine Pharmacology." *Dumbarton Oaks Papers Symposium on Byzantine Medicine* 38, (1984): 213-32.

⁹⁵ Theophrastus, *Enquiry into Plants*, IX, 217.

⁹⁶ *Ibid.*, IX, 251.

without it being known. As an evolutionary instinct in every species, plants that are harmful or beneficial would have been determined through any number of senses. The resulting ingestion, touch, or smell of the plant would either cause sickness or death or it would heal the being interacting with the plant. This evolutionary instinct is the same with all harmful or beneficiary things; from saber-toothed cats like *Smilodon* to *Dodos*, humans have figured out what is dangerous and what isn't through trial and error. The remaining information from Book IX contains all of the specific information on the medicinal plants Theophrastus described. This information was compiled and sorted in Table 1 in the Appendix.

Book IX of *Historia Plantarum* contains about seventy-three herbs and herbal remedies. Every plant that was mentioned having medicinal properties was placed into Table 1 in Appendix I. Plants that were not specifically named by Theophrastus were indistinguishable for the breadth of this study, but in the future it would be interesting to dig deeper into other ancient and Medieval texts on plants and identify those plants that were not named. The study involved cataloging each plant mentioned along with its useful information: the name of the plant in *Historia Plantarum*, how the plant was prepared and used medicinally, the reference for the location of the plant in *Historia Plantarum*, the Latin name given to the plants by Kurt Sprengel in the plant index, and finally the number of medicinal compounds found in that plant genus according to the Dictionary of Natural Products (DNP).

A good indicator of whether or not a plant has been studied is to examine the number of compounds isolated and identified from the plant species. Each medicinally active plant from *Historia Plantarum* Book IX was organized based on the number of compounds identified from the DNP through a genus search. The results yielded that the following plants have the least medicinal compounds identified: Herakles all-heal (*Opopanax hispidus*), the "blood-stancher" plant (*Bothriochloa ischaemum*), hartwort (*Tordylium officinale*), hemlock (*Conium maculatum*), and mandrake (*Mandragora officinarum*). Both hemlock and mandrake, although they do not have many compounds listed in the DNP, have been studied thoroughly for their medicinal benefits, mainly due to the presence of

alkaloids.⁹⁷ Also both of these plants have been studied throughout history for their medicinal and poisonous qualities. A theory known as the Doctrine of Signatures (DOS) explains how humans have discovered medicinal plants based on physical features that mirror the diseases they cure. For example, mandrake has human-shaped leaves, which led humans to believe that the plant was beneficial to a human, a panacea.⁹⁸ Taking all of this into mind, hemlock and mandrake must be eliminated from further investigation in this study.

From there, any of the remaining plants can be chosen. For the sake of brevity, the hartwort (*Tordylium officinale*) will be the plant further investigated. In *De Materia Medica*, where hartwort is mentioned in an abortifacient remedy, Dioscorides also mentions its benefits as a menstrual regulator and emmenagogue.⁹⁹ Despite the references in Dioscorides, hartwort doesn't appear in the pharmacological record. The work of Bruno Tirillini on the "essential oil composition of *Tordylium apulum* L. from Italy" showed no medicinal activity for the leaves of the plant.¹⁰⁰ Therefore the possibility to discover potential medicinally active compounds in hartwort species is plausible. Therefore this plant is a prime candidate for the next step in the research process, screening a crude extract of the plant for antimicrobial and/or antibacterial activity. If the plant has no activity, then move to the next plant in the sequence until an interesting result arises, much like ancient scientists would have conducted experimentation.

Through the information given in Theophrastus' works and the ability to utilize modern instrumentation for research, the plants and remedies in *Historia Plantarum* are testable for activity. Theophrastus left modern scholars a wealth of information, along with the rest of the ancient writers of pharmacology. When one looks deeper into the texts of Theophrastus, it is clear that he was working on an

⁹⁷ Lewis, W. H.; Elvin-Lewis, M. P. F. *Medical Botany*. (New York: John Wiley and Sons, 2007).

⁹⁸ Bennett, B.C. "Doctrine of Signatures: An Explanation of Medicinal Plant Discovery or Dissemination of Knowledge?" *Economic Botany* 61, (2007): 246.

⁹⁹ Riddle, J.M. *Contraception and Abortion from the Ancient World to the Renaissance*. (USA: Harvard University Press, 1994), 78.

¹⁰⁰ Tirinilli, B. et al. "Essential Oil Composition of *Tordylium apulum* L. from Italy." *Journal of Essential Oil Research* 18(1), (2006).

intellectual level not far from modern scientist. Limited by the times he worked in, Theophrastus established a taxonomic system that would be utilized until Linnaeus and the pharmacological information gathered by himself and his pupils remained influential until the Renaissance when it was rediscovered.

CHAPTER II. PLINY THE ELDER AND *HISTORIA NATURALIS**INTRODUCTION*

Pliny was born in Novum Comum around 23/24 C.E. He was from wealth, which allowed Pliny to begin a career in the military only available to men of the Equestrian class.¹⁰¹ Pliny “represents a recognizable social phenomenon of the period: that of men brought up in a comparatively simple life style and reacting with somewhat puritanical naiveté to a more sophisticated one.”¹⁰² Pliny’s military career could have been like some where he was simply a “pen soldier”, but he served many posts “which suggests a quite serious interest in this part of his career.”¹⁰³ “It is reasonable to deduce from his reference to autopsy in Germany that he actually took part in a campaign east of the Rhine conducted by Domitius Corbulo.”¹⁰⁴ He later served next to the son of the later emperor Vespasian, Titus, to whom he dedicated the *Historia Naturalis*.¹⁰⁵ During his time in the military Pliny began his writing career with an essay on cavalry maneuver, *De Iacultatione Equestri*.¹⁰⁶ Reynolds makes a point that, “It is also evident from the *Natural History* that he kept his eyes and ears open, curiosity alert, to see what he could see and learn in or near the frontier area.”¹⁰⁷

Throughout his military career, Pliny was procurator “of the largest and most important division of Spain, Hispania Tarraconensis,” where his role mostly involved being there for the emperor’s financial affairs.¹⁰⁸ Other posts credited to Pliny are Gallia Narbonensis, which he would have conceivably passed through on his way to

¹⁰¹ Reynolds, J. “The Elder Pliny and his Times.” In *Science in the Early Roman Empire: Pliny the Elder, his Sources and Influences*, ed. Roger French and Frank Greenway (Kent: Biddles Ltd, 1986), 1.

¹⁰² *Ibid.*, 1-2.

¹⁰³ *Ibid.*, 3.

¹⁰⁴ *Ibid.*, 4.

¹⁰⁵ *Ibid.*, 4.

¹⁰⁶ *Ibid.*, 5.

¹⁰⁷ *Ibid.*, 5.

¹⁰⁸ Healy, J. *Pliny the Elder on Science and Technology*. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2003), 4.

Germany for private retreat, and Africa, which would have more likely been for business administration than private reasoning (although even these are debatable among scholars).¹⁰⁹ Pliny played minor roles in the politics of the Julio-Claudian era and a larger role under Vespasian. In 59 C.E., Pliny returned to Rome seeking a career in law. However, it is unknown what Pliny did with his time until the death of Nero, with some saying he may have retreated into private life and focused on his works on grammar.¹¹⁰ One thing that is for sure is that Pliny did not like Nero, citing him “the enemy of mankind” and Pliny openly criticizes his extravagances.¹¹¹ Out of his disliking of Nero came an opportunity when Vespasian rose to power, as Pliny was given a place in the emperor’s council.¹¹²

Above all of his military and political aspirations and accomplishments, he was a “glutton for information, curious about, though not seriously questioning about, all that came his way; constantly reading or being read to; wasting no minute; believing that even the worst book might yield a grain of fact.”¹¹³ Pliny the Younger furthers this conception because his uncle optimized his time. “He was a fanatical time-saver, short-sleeper and night-worker: even when he was in the bath or sedan chair, he used the time for reading or dictating. Reading aloud even took place during meals.”¹¹⁴

Overall, Pliny wrote on a plethora of topics, as seen in the *Historia Naturalis*. The encyclopedia includes thirty-seven books covering mathematics, astronomy, geography, zoology, human physiology, botany, pharmacology, minerals, and other interests he held. Most interesting to the purposes of this study are those books on botany and pharmacology. Although he himself doesn’t directly observe and record data like Theophrastus did in *De Causis Plantarum* and *Historia Plantarum*, Pliny’s

¹⁰⁹ Reynolds, “The Elder Pliny and his Times”, 8; Healy, *Pliny the Elder*, 7-8.

¹¹⁰ Healy, *Pliny the Elder*, 6.

¹¹¹ *Ibid.*, 6.

¹¹² *Ibid.*, 6-7.

¹¹³ Reynolds, J. “The Elder Pliny and his Times”, 9.

¹¹⁴ Locher, A. “The Structure of Pliny the Elder’s Natural History.” In *Science in the Early Roman Empire: Pliny the Elder, his Sources and Influences*, ed. Roger French and Frank Greenway (Kent: Biddles Ltd, 1986), 25.

divulgence into the world of pharmacology and botany influenced the Roman, Medieval, and Renaissance equivalently to that of Theophrastus.

STRUCTURE AND STYLE

In his history of Roman Literature, philologist Eduard Norden called the *Natural History* “a literary monstrosity”.¹¹⁵ The fact is that the majority of time Pliny is not considered an author. One serious misconception on the part of previous philologists and scholars that worked with the *Natural History* is the fact that it is a work not that is meant to be categorized with the great authors and poets of ancient history. Locher states, “it is written for the common people, for the mass of peasants and artisans, and only then for those who devote themselves to their studies for leisure.”¹¹⁶ Something fascinating about the *Historia Naturalis* is the sheer volume of the text. This must have taken Pliny countless hours to read, dictate, and organize the information into retrievable parts. Locher points out that Pliny included notes into his *commentarii* on works:

“That can only have happened in two different ways...Pliny either dictated *adnotationes* into the *commentarii* to serve as retrieval aids, for instance in the margin, or these *adnotationes* were added by Pliny himself in the margin of the books he read or were read to him, and contained hints as to where the excerpt in question was to be included in the *commentarii*. In this case the *commentarii* would then have been a kind of structured collection of materials for the *Natural History*. Pliny would then have already been able to mention to his slaves the scrolls in which the required material was to be found in individual cases.”¹¹⁷

Essentially, Pliny utilized a handmade instrument that functioned like a modern computerized system. Thusly, his praise upon himself is justified, “there is no one among us who has attempted the same thing, no one among the Greeks who has

¹¹⁵Ibid., 20.

¹¹⁶ Ibid., 21.

¹¹⁷ Ibid., 27.

dealt as an individual with all this together.”¹¹⁸ Altogether, Pliny’s wealth of information catalogued in the *Historia Naturalis* is a direct result his contemporaries and predecessors hard work.

Pliny did give firsthand accounts of technologies such as those he witnessed during his administration of Hispania Tarraconensis¹¹⁹, but the majority of the *Historia Naturalis* is cited information from other ancient philosophers and authors. Pertaining to the authors on pharmacology, Pliny relies on Dioscorides and Celsius, who thusly relied on classical Greek authors like Hippocrates and Theophrastus.¹²⁰ The accuracy of the information is of course directly related to the accuracy of the source, but Pliny seems to not discriminate when citing inaccuracies as can be seen from his fascination with *mirabilia*.

Pliny’s poor reputation stems back to “Leoniceno’s attempts to discredit Pliny’s contribution to ‘science’.”¹²¹ Later scholars greatly exaggerate the poor Latin grammar and stylized writing that is Pliny’s *Natural History* and Healy defends the quality of Pliny’s writing:¹²²

“Fortunately, any but the most superficial study of the *Natural History*, soon reveals the wildly exaggerated nature of these generalizations. The fact that this unique encyclopedic work, unlike other, has not only survived to the present day, but continues to excite the interest of scholars in different disciplines, is surely proof enough of the importance of its contribution to our knowledge of the early imperial period.”¹²³

This interest in the *Natural History* from modern scholars from many disciplines is why it makes it such an important work of ancient science and ancient pharmacology. With so few texts surviving from antiquity on ancient pharmacology

¹¹⁸ Ibid., 28.

¹¹⁹ Healy, J. *Pliny the Elder on Science and Technology*, 57-58.

¹²⁰ Scarborough, J. “Early Byzantine Pharmacology.” *Dumbarton Oaks Papers Symposium on Byzantine Medicine* 38, (1984): 213-32.

¹²¹ Healy, J. *Pliny the Elder on Science and Technology*, 80.

¹²² Ibid., 79-81.

¹²³ Ibid., 81.

and botany, Pliny's work becomes that much more important in regards Roman knowledge on medicinal plants.

A persistent problem plaguing the *Natural History* is the restrictions of Latin in the field of medicine. Healy mentions that this is the area of the *Natural History* which Pliny owes his greatest debt.¹²⁴ "This was largely due to the fact that medicine entered Roman life from Ionia through Alexandrian anatomy and physiology."¹²⁵ Similarly like medicine, drugs and remedies also retain their Greek nomenclature.¹²⁶ Also, the rhetorical style of writing in Pliny's time is problematic. His rhetoric heavily influenced his writing style, one that would come with much criticism. Many times throughout the *Natural History*, Pliny writes similarly to Theophrastus in that he gives facts in a "dry style, using abrupt sentences which create a staccato effect." Whereas other times he "can write in a vivid and entertaining manner."¹²⁷ Regardless of Pliny's pitfalls as a writer, his contributions to ancient science later resonate throughout the Middle Ages and the Renaissance, making it mandatory to examine in terms of ancient pharmacology.

HISTORIA NATURALIS (NATURAL HISTORY)

Books XX-XXXII handle all things categorized under 'remedies' according to Pliny and his sources. Book XX "Remedies derived from garden plants" up to Book XXVII "A description of plants, and of the remedies derived from them" outlines the entirety of Pliny's collected knowledge of remedies derived from flora. Books XXVIII-XXX all deal with remedies derived from terrestrial creatures, something no doubt interesting, but not directly relevant to this study. Book XXXI deals with remedies derived from aquatic production, which contains an interesting section on sponges (XXXI.47), a relevant topic of discussion for the current climate of pharmacology research ongoing. Finally, Book XXXII contains remedies derived

¹²⁴ Ibid., 89.

¹²⁵ Ibid., 89.

¹²⁶ Ibid., 89.

¹²⁷ Ibid., 99.

from aquatic animals, again, a section of the *Natural History* that isn't directly relevant to the discussion of ancient plant pharmacology. This plethora of information which contains over 1000 plants¹²⁸ is too much to sift through in the context of this study, but by looking at a few of the books that contain important pharmacological information, conclusions on the importance and nature of *Historia Naturalis* can be drawn.

Therefore particular interest will be paid to Books XX, XXI, XXV, and XXVII in order to examine ancient pharmacology in Roman imperial period. Book XX begins Pliny's adventure into world of botanical remedies through examining garden botanicals. Pliny starts this book with an introduction to his exploration into the world of medicinal remedies:

“ We are now about to enter upon an examination of the greatest of all the operations of Nature—we are about to discourse to man upon his aliments, and to compel him to admit that he is ignorant by what means he exists. And let no one, misled by the apparent triviality of the names which we shall have to employ, regard this subject as one that is frivolous or contemptible: for we shall here have to set forth the state of peace or of war which exists between the various departments of Nature, the hatreds or friendships which are maintained by objects dumb and destitute of sense, and all, too, created—a wonderful subject for our contemplation!—for the sake of man alone. To these states, known to the Greeks by the respective appellations "sympathia" and "antipathia," we are indebted for the first principles of all things; for hence it is that water has the property of extinguishing fire, that the sun absorbs water, that the moon produces it, and that each of those heavenly bodies is from time to time eclipsed by the other.

Hence it is, too, descending from the contemplation of a loftier sphere, that the loadstone possesses the property of attracting iron, and another stone, again, that of repelling it: and that the diamond, that pride of luxury and opulence, though infrangible by every other object, and presenting a resistance that cannot be overcome, is broken asunder by a he-goat's blood—in addition to numerous other marvels of which we shall have to speak on more appropriate occasions, equal

¹²⁸ Stannard, J. 'Medicinal plants and folk remedies in Pliny, *Historia Naturalis*.' *History and Philosophy of the Life Sciences* 4, (1982): 3-23.

to this or still more wonderful even. My only request is that pardon may be accorded me for beginning with objects of a more humble nature, though still so greatly conducive to our health—I mean the garden plants, of which I shall now proceed to speak.”¹²⁹

By starting with garden plants, Pliny is introducing himself into the subject matter with the most studied plants from previous philosophers. Covering everything from onions¹³⁰, garlic¹³¹, and cabbage¹³² to many herbs such as mint¹³³, fennel¹³⁴, dill¹³⁵, and parsley¹³⁶, Pliny catalogues some of the most medicinally important plants known to the ancients. Herbs being used as medicine date back as far as written history and surely would be traced back to the earliest modern humans.

The inclusion of exotic plants is prevalent in both Theophrastus’ and Pliny’s texts, more so in Pliny though. Roman trade to India and other Far East lands allowed for the influx of exotic spices and oils. One particular example that is an intriguing is the Indian pepper. Pliny catalogues the information in the following manner:

“Piperitis, which we have already mentioned as being called ‘siliquastrum,’ is taken in drink for epilepsy. Castor used to give a description of it to the following effect: ‘The stalk of it is long and red, with the knots lying close together; the leaves are similar to those of the laurel, and the seed is white and slender, like pepper in taste.’ He described it also as being beneficial to the gums and teeth, imparting sweetness to the breath, and dispelling flatulency.”¹³⁷

Pliny further describes the many illnesses and diseases that pepper, in conjuncture with other plants and spices, can cure. The list includes: fever¹³⁸, alopecia¹³⁹, aches

¹²⁹ Plin. NH XX. 1.

¹³⁰ Ibid., XX. 23.

¹³¹ Ibid., XX. 20.

¹³² Ibid., XX. 33.

¹³³ Ibid., XX. 53.

¹³⁴ Ibid., XX. 95.

¹³⁵ Ibid., XX. 74.

¹³⁶ Ibid., XX. 44.

¹³⁷ Ibid., XX. 66.

¹³⁸ Ibid., XXII. 11; Ibid., XXII. 74; Ibid., XXVI. 71; Ibid., XXX. 30, Ibid., XXXII. 38. 10.

¹³⁹ Ibid., XXII. 49; Ibid., XXIX. 34. 6.

and pains¹⁴⁰, spider, insect, and snake bites¹⁴¹, intestinal worms¹⁴², cough¹⁴³, women's diseases¹⁴⁴, hallucinations¹⁴⁵, infections¹⁴⁶, jaundice¹⁴⁷, diarrhea¹⁴⁸, and as an aphrodisiac¹⁴⁹. This list of the uses of pepper represents either its true effectiveness as a drug or a component of a potion or antidote, its characteristics as a spice, or its mystical qualities. Modern science has shed some light that reinforces and dismisses some of the pepper's use in remedies. Results from research shows that the long pepper (*Piper cubeba* but known in ancient times as *Piper longum*¹⁵⁰) possesses anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective, antiallergic, antimicrobial, and antioxidant properties.¹⁵¹ Also, pepper (*Piper nigrum*) possesses analgesic, carminative, stimulant, febrifuge, antioxidant and antimicrobial properties.¹⁵² Therefore, although lacking in the modern instrumentation that makes science today so accurate, ancient physicians and author's deduced important information from plants in various manners.

Pliny's description shows the nature of his writing style and structure. Although seemingly knowledgeable on the subject, Pliny still relies on other sources to account the medicinal nature of the plant. This is a fundamental principle that Pliny adopts from his predecessors. Healy notes, "The volume of research sources and authorities consulted by Pliny mirrors his diligence and commitment to research. The *Natural History* contains 20000 facts, from 2000 works by 100 chosen

¹⁴⁰ Ibid., XXII. 15. 13; Ibid., XXIV. 118; Ibid., XXVII. 28; Ibid., XXVII. 105; Ibid., XXX. 22 ;Ibid., XXXI. 46. 10; Ibid., XXXII. 28.

¹⁴¹ Ibid., XXV. 55; Ibid., XXIX. 27.

¹⁴² Ibid., XXII. 74.

¹⁴³ Ibid., XXIII. 78.

¹⁴⁴ Ibid., XXIV. 59; Ibid., XXVI. 90.

¹⁴⁵ Ibid., XXIV. 102.

¹⁴⁶ Ibid., XXVI. 68.

¹⁴⁷ Ibid., XXXII. 31.

¹⁴⁸ Ibid., XXIX. 11. 3.

¹⁴⁹ Ibid., XXVIII. 30.

¹⁵⁰ Miller, J.I., *The Spice Trade of the Roman Empire* (London: Oxford University Press, 1969).

¹⁵¹ Gupta, M. "Pharmacological Properties and Traditional Therapeutic Uses of Important Indian Spices: A Review." *International Journal of Food Properties* 13, (2010), 1104.

¹⁵² Ibid., 1104.

authors. These figures, however, represent a conservative estimate, since no fewer than 146 Roman and 326 foreign authors are quoted!"¹⁵³ Pliny also acknowledges his own careful research:

"You will count as proof of my professionalism that fact that I have prefaced these books with the names of my authorities. In my opinion such acknowledgement of those who have contributed to one's success-unlike the practice of most of the authors I have mentioned-is a not ungracious gesture and abounds with honourable modesty. For, you ought to know that when I compared authorities, I found that writers of bygone times had been copied by the most reliable and modern authors, word for word, without acknowledgement."¹⁵⁴

Therefore, through Pliny's writing, the myriad of botanists, pharmacologists, and physicians in later centuries were able to use the information observed by the philosophers of Classical Greece and the Roman Republic due to the transmission of information by Pliny the Elder. As one of the most reliable sections of the *Natural History* on previous sources, the books on remedies do not lose their weight solely because Pliny isn't the primary source of information. In fact, modern historians are constantly looking for and creating databases of information. The information that is compiled into databases becomes useful on a much larger scale. Pliny's *Natural History* effectively acts as an ancient database of all the knowledge of the day, allowing anyone who had a copy to access its wealth of information. Book XX contains 99 different plants and their corresponding remedies. Only examining this one book doesn't do Pliny's compilation justice, so therefore examining Books XXI, XXV, and XXVII will formulate a better-rounded review.

Book XXI, "An account of flowers, and those used for chaplets more particularly," handles all remedies and the more superstitious side of chaplets, or amulets. Although an important examination of magic in the ancient world, digging deeper into the ancient pseudoscientific side of medicine is not relevant to this thesis. Looking past this part of the book, the remedies contained in this section are an important look into common flowers and shrubs being used in the ancient world.

¹⁵³ Healy, *Pliny the Elder on Science and Technology*, 77.

¹⁵⁴ *Ibid.*, 77-78.

Roses¹⁵⁵, lilies¹⁵⁶, narcissus¹⁵⁷, and violet¹⁵⁸ are all included in this book that include common flowers and exotic flowers. Book XXI contains valuable information but Book XXV has a very important principle within it, that wild plants were paramount to ancient medicine.

Wild plants maintain a major role to ancient society due to the fact that cultivating plants was very difficult. Pliny mentions that peppers were not able to be cultivated in Italy because it lost its entire flavor.¹⁵⁹ Therefore, this grouping of plants is one of the most unique and relevant sources for remedies. He begins by examining the Latin and Greek knowledge up to his point. He states that the Latin authors haven't covered the topic of wild plants except for the ventures of M. Cato and C. Valgius¹⁶⁰, and before them a freedman, Pompeius Lenæus, and Mithridates which Pliny states, "This prince was the first discoverer too of the various kinds of antidotes, one of which, indeed, still retains his name; and it is generally supposed that he was the first to employ the blood of the ducks of Pontus as an ingredient in antidotes, from the circumstance that they derive their nutriment from poisons."¹⁶¹ In terms of the Greek authors, Pliny has reservations about their work:

"Among them, Crateuas, Dionysius, and Metrodorus, adopted a very attractive method of description, though one which has done little more than prove the remarkable difficulties which attended it. It was their plan to delineate the various plants in colours, and then to add in writing a description of the properties which they possessed. Pictures, however, are very apt to mislead, and more particularly where such a number of tints is required, for the imitation of nature with any success; in addition to which, the diversity of copyists from the original paintings, and their comparative degrees of skill, add very considerably to the chances of losing the necessary degree of resemblance to the originals. And then, besides, it is not sufficient to

¹⁵⁵ Plin. NH XXI. 73.

¹⁵⁶ Ibid., XXI. 74.

¹⁵⁷ Ibid., XXI. 75.

¹⁵⁸ Ibid., XXI. 76.

¹⁵⁹ Warmington, E.H., *The Commerce between the Roman Empire and India*, 2nd ed. (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1974), 182.

¹⁶⁰ Plin. NH XXV. 2.

¹⁶¹ Ibid., XXV. 3.

delineate a plant as it appears at one period only, as it presents a different appearance at each of the four seasons of the year.”¹⁶²

Pliny then goes further into the treatment of plants by Greek authors. He brings up the stories of Medea and Circe, Orpheus, the works of Pythagoras and Democritus.¹⁶³ Pliny later goes on to describe the difficulties that come about when discovering medicinally relevant wild plants.

Pliny brings up many similar issues that are plaguing the scientific community today. He mentions that those “who are acquainted with them are unwilling to impart their knowledge”, them being the wild plants which have medicinal properties.¹⁶⁴ Now although dissemination is a common practice in modern science, the lack of free databases and open-sourced journals allow for those who only have the funding to purchase the journals to access to information. Also of serious consequence, Pliny mentions, “Added to all this, there is no well-ascertained method to guide us to the acquisition of this kind of knowledge; for, as to the discoveries that have been made already, they have been due, some of them, to mere accident, and others again, to say the truth, to the interposition of the Deity.”¹⁶⁵ This problem of no systematic scientific method is also one brought up during the introduction and previous chapter on Theophrastus and one that not surprisingly had been fixed in 400 years. Pliny followed the methodology of the time; therefore critiquing his works based on modern standards is not an effective exercise.

The remaining information contained in Book XXV consists of accounts on plants discovered and uncultivated. These include mandragora¹⁶⁶, black hellebore¹⁶⁷, euphorbia¹⁶⁸, etc. This information provides insight into the more common medicinal practices of the era. Like spices and herbs, wild plants would

¹⁶² Ibid., XXV. 4.

¹⁶³ Ibid., XXV. 5.

¹⁶⁴ Ibid., XXV. 6.

¹⁶⁵ Ibid., XXV. 6.

¹⁶⁶ Ibid., XXV. 94.

¹⁶⁷ Ibid., XXV. 22.

¹⁶⁸ Ibid., XXV. 38.

have been utilized on a daily basis for their medicinal qualities. Pliny states at the beginning of this book the importance placed on wild plants:

“The more highly esteemed plants of which I am now about to speak, and which are produced by the earth for medicinal purposes solely, inspire me with admiration of the industry and laborious research displayed by the ancients. Indeed there is nothing that they have not tested by experiment or left untried; no discovery of theirs which they have not disclosed, or which they have not been desirous to leave for the benefit of posterity. We, on the contrary, at the present day, make it our object to conceal and suppress the results of our labours, and to defraud our fellow-men of blessings even which have been purchased by others.”¹⁶⁹

Pliny’s desire to disseminate this knowledge clearly is against the practices of his time as he states in the passage above. The Classical Greek authors before him released all of their knowledge upon the world whereas the Romans disregard this and hold knowledge closely. This pursuit of knowledge by Classical Greek authors and others in ancient times that Pliny describes as ‘ancients’ continues fluidly into Book XXVII.

“A description of plants, and of the remedies derived from them” is the vague title of Book XXVII. A more applicable name for the book may be “A description of foreign plants, and of the remedies derived from them” due to the inclusion of a large number of plants from around the empire. These plants include aloe and its’ twenty-nine remedies, of which the best is found in India, then the Asiatic provinces, and Judea¹⁷⁰; four species of absinthium or wormwood and its’ forty-eight remedies, deriving from Gaul, Pontus, and Italy¹⁷¹; glycysside and twenty remedies, found in Greece¹⁷²; rhacoma and thirty-six remedies from the regions beyond Pontus.¹⁷³ This book contains important information for the nature of ancient medicine. Plants from other nations, specifically foreign, exotic lands, were extremely valuable to the botanists and philosophers of the ancient world. The pseudoscience of mysticism

¹⁶⁹ Ibid., XXV. 1.

¹⁷⁰ Ibid., XXVII. 5.

¹⁷¹ Ibid., XXVII. 28.

¹⁷² Ibid., XXVII. 60.

¹⁷³ Ibid., XXVII. 105.

and magic, although unquantifiable, was an essential part to ancient pharmacology, as mentioned in the introduction. So plants from other lands naturally held a mystic quality to them, mostly due to local myths and legends involving the plants.

The four books further investigated above are an ample examination of Pliny's contributions to ancient pharmacology and medicine. Regarding Pliny's lack of expertise, it becomes superfluous due to his meticulous citation of sources and the accounts of his examination of all of the available materials from his nephew, Pliny the Younger. Pliny's critics consistently cite his fascination with *mirabilia* as a fatal flaw of his 'sciences'¹⁷⁴, but Pliny is simply a product of his time:

“Naturally occurring and man-made oddities, listed throughout the *Natural History*, are part of a long tradition which has its beginnings in Homer's *Odyssey*, where Odysseus encounters the Sirens, Polyphemus, Scylla and Charybdis, and other legendary creatures. By the Hellenistic period, writings specifically devoted to *mirabilia* were widespread, although many are known only from subsequently lost works: reference and quotations preserved are an important source for their study.”¹⁷⁵ Pliny's examples of *mirabilia* are mostly concentrated to zoology, where he describes races of men with special powers, human freaks, extraordinarily long-living people, and such fantastical creatures as the hippocentaur.¹⁷⁶

This fascination with the strange didn't come without reservations. “He expresses his unwillingness to accept Greek ‘tall stories’ (‘fabulosa’) that he considers to be an insult to the intelligence”.¹⁷⁷ Even though a flawed aspect of his work, “this interest in the unusual and sometimes bizarre, may, in a sense, constitute a logical, preliminary stage on the way to genuine ‘scientific’ curiosity”.¹⁷⁸ Looking past the *mirabilia* mentioned, the books previously mentioned in Pliny's *Historia Naturalis* give an intimate look into the mind of both ancient pharmacologists and of Pliny the Elder himself.

¹⁷⁴ Healy, *Pliny the Elder on Science and Technology*, 64.

¹⁷⁵ *Ibid.*, 63.

¹⁷⁶ *Ibid.*, 65-67.

¹⁷⁷ *Ibid.*, 65.

¹⁷⁸ *Ibid.*, 70.

In the context of this study, Pliny's *Historia Naturalis* must be confined to its own category. There are no major works remaining from the ancient world that compare to Pliny's. Although encyclopedic works remain from the likes of Varro, Verrius Flaccus, and Alexander Polyhistor, of which Pliny is indebted to all, no author has attempted to cover so much material.¹⁷⁹ As previously mentioned, Pliny's work equates to the modern database one can find on the Internet. The information is plentiful but lacks depth. Pliny's intention was never to investigate the validity of the accounts he read or heard. This is why Pliny's 'science' has been questioned further, mainly because his goal was to not be scientific, but to be informative. A basic principle of the scientific method is to dig deeper into the results of an experiment and question the results, but one must understand and look into Pliny's work and see that this is not his goal. Although Pliny doesn't scientifically evaluate the accounts he copied and transcribed, the information inside in conjecture with other ancient, Medieval, Renaissance, Enlightenment, and Modern accounts make it one of the most valuable pieces of writing to examine the ancient world, the thinking of ancient peoples, and the processes people went through to discover information.

¹⁷⁹ Ibid., 46-47.

APPENDIX I.

TABLE 1. CATALOG OF MEDICINAL PLANTS FROM *HISTORIA PLANTARUM*

<i>Plants in Book IX of HP</i>	<i>How it is prepared and used</i>	<i>Book Reference</i>	<i>Latin names as given by Sprengel¹⁸⁰</i>	<i>DNP hits for Latin names provided by Sprengel</i>
Alexanders/'horse celery'	"Serviceable in cases of strangury and for those suffering from stone, being administered in sweet white wine"	IX.XV.5	<i>Smyrniolum olusatrum</i>	34
All-heal (Asklepios)	"It is said that it is good to scrape and drink it against bites of reptiles, to take it in a posset of honey for disorders of the spleen, when the blood collects about it, and against headache; that it is of use also in other obscure troubles, and against stomachache, if scraped and taken in wine. It is said also to be able to prevent long periods of sickness. Again for running sores one may sprinkle it on in hot wine, first washing the place, while for dry sores one may soak it in wine and apply and plaster."	IX.XI.2	<i>Prunella vulgaris/Ferula nodosa</i>	638

¹⁸⁰ Theophrastus, *Enquiry into Plants*, 437-485.

All-heal (Chaeronea)	"They use it for the bites of snakes, spiders, vipers and other reptiles with it mixed with olive-oil. In treating a snake-bite they use a plaster of it, and also give a draught of it mixed with vinegar; and they also say that it is good for sores when mixed with wine and olive-oil, and for tumours when mixed with honey."	IX.XI.1	<i>Prunella vulgaris/Inula helenium</i>	405
All-heal (Herakles)	"In taste it is somewhat bitter, in smell like pure frankincense; it is good to drink against epilepsy, mixed with the rennet of a seal in the proportion of one to four, or in sweet wine against pain in the stomach; it may be used dry for running sores, and mixed with honey for dry ones."	IX.XI.3	<i>Prunella vulgaris/Opopanax hispidus</i>	6
All-heal (Syrian)	"Uses in cases of miscarriage and for disorders of the bladder"; "which is called <i>khalbane</i> , is used in cases of miscarriage and also for sprains and such-like troubles; also for the ears, and to strengthen the voice."; "used in childbirth, for diseases of women, and for flatulence in beast of burden. It is also useful in making the iris-perfume because of its fragrance."; "the seed is stronger than the root."	IX.IX.2	<i>Prunella vulgaris</i>	19

All-heal (two other kinds)	"There are also other kinds of all-heal, of which one has a fine leaf, the other not; the properties of both kinds are the same; namely they are used as a pessary for women, and a plaster may be made of them mixed with meal for spreading sores as well as for ordinary sores."	IX.XI.4	<i>Ferulago galbanifera</i>	24
Birthwort	<p>"Is best for sores on the head and other sores, also for bites or reptiles, for inducing sleep and for disorders of the womb. It is directed that it should be applied as a plaster, steeped in water, and for the other purposes should be given shredded into honey and olive-oil: for snake-bites it should be taken in sour wine and also used as a plaster on the bite: to induce sleep it should be scraped up and administered in black dry wine; in cases of <i>prolapsus uteri</i> a lotion of it mixed with water should be applied."</p> <p>"Many uses of it for various purposes are enumerated; it is best for bruises on the head, good also for other wounds, against snake-bites, to produce sleep, for the womb as a pessary: for some purposes it is soaked with water and applied as a plaster, for others it is scraped into honey and olive-oil: against snake-bites it is drunk in sour wine and also sprinkled over the bite; to induce sleep it is given pounded up in black dry wine: in cases of <i>prolapses uteri</i> it is used in water as a lotion."</p>	IX.XIII.3	<i>Aristolochia rotunda</i>	324
Black hellebore	"Fatal to horses, oxen, and pigs, wherefore non of these animals eat it"; "men also purify horses and sheep with it, at the same time chanting an incantation; and they put it to several other uses."	IX.X.1-4	<i>Helleborus cyclophyllis</i>	68

Black poppy	"Mixing with it two parts of 'black poppy'"	IX.XI.9	<i>Papaver hybridum</i>	246
Blood-stancher	"Which stops and prevents the flow of blood, some say if the vein is merely pricked, others even if it is deeply cut into."	IX.XV.3	<i>Andropogon ischaemum</i>	7
Carrot	"An Arcadian drug".	IX.XV.5	<i>Daucus carota</i>	103
Centaury	"And then they say the juice of the centaury is mixed with it."	IX.XI.6	<i>Centaurea salonitana</i>	351
Chamaelon (dark/black)	"It has the property of expelling leprosy; for this it is given pounded up in vinegar, or else this it is given pounded up in vinegar, or else scrapings of it are made into a plaster; and it is also used for the white leprosy. This plant is also fatal to dogs.	IX.XII.2	<i>Cardopatium corymbosum (Houttuynia?)</i>	2
Chamaelon (white)	"In the one case the root is white, stout, and sweet, and it has a heavy smell; they say that when cooked it is serviceable against flux, it is chopped up like radishes and the pieces strung on a rush; it is also good against the broad maw-worm; the patient first eats a bunch of raisins and then drinks about an eighth of a pint of this scraped up in a draught of dry wine. It is fatal to dogs and pigs; to kill a dog it is well mixed up in a meal paste with oil and water, to kill a pig it is mixed with 'mountain cabbage' (spurge).It is given to a women in sweet wine-lees or sweet wine. And if one wished to discover whether a man that is sick will recover, they say that he should be washed with this for three days, and, if he survives the experience, he will recover. Some actually call it the thistle."	IX.XII.1	<i>Delphinium staphisagria</i>	491

Cnidian berry	"Larger than that of pepper, and far stronger in its heating power; wherefore, when it is given as a pill (for it is given to open the bowels) they knead it up in a piece of bread or dough: otherwise it burns the throat."	IX.XX.2	<i>Daphne Gnidium</i>	223
Cyclamen	"Is used for suppurating boils; also as a pessary for women and, mixed with honey, for dressing wounds...They say that the root is a good charm for inducing rapid delivery and as a love potion-when they have dug it up, they burn it, and then, having steeped the ashes in wine, make little balls like those made of wine- lees which we use as soap"; "The juice for purgings of the head, for which purpose it is mixed with honey and poured in; it also conduces to drunkenness, if one is given a draught of wine in which it has been steeped."	IX.IX.3	<i>Cyclamen graecum</i>	37
Daukon	" <i>Daukon</i> of excellent quality grows in the district of Patrai in Achaia, and is heating by nature: it has a black root."	IX.XX.2	<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	91
Deadly-nightshade	"The fruit of deadly nightshade is peculiar in being black and like a grape and like wine in taste"	VI.II.8	<i>Atropa belladonna</i>	26

Dittany	"Is peculiar to Crete. This plant is marvelous in virtue and is useful for many purposes, but especially for women in childbirth. They use the leaves, not the twigs nor the fruit: and the leaf is useful for many other purposes, but above all, as was said, against difficult labour in women; for it is said that either it makes labour quite easy or at least it confessedly makes the pains to cease: it is given as a draught in water. The story of the arrows is also said to be true,-that, if goats eat it when they have been shot, it rids them of the arrow. Such then is dittany and such its properties."	IX.XVI.3	<i>Origanum dictamnus</i>	52
Ebony	"It is useful against ophthalmia, and is rubbed on a whetstone for that use."	IX.XX.4	<i>Diospyros ebenum</i>	234
Edderwort	"The root of edderwort given in milk is useful for stopping a cough."	IX.XX.2	<i>Dracunculus vulgaris</i>	31
False dittany	"For it is serviceable in the same ways, but is feebler and not nearly so powerful. The virtue of dittany is perceived directly it is taken into the mouth: for a small piece of it has a very warming effect. "	IX.XVI.2	<i>Ballota pseudodictamnus</i>	38
Feverwort	"Feverwort (whose root is thick and compact) for ten or twelve [years]"	IX.XIV.1	<i>Erythraea centaurium</i>	89
Frankincense	"Wherefore these, as well as frankincense, are used as antidotes for poisoning by hemlock."	IX.XX.1	<i>Boswellia carteri</i>	64

Garlic	"For hellebore too soon makes the head heavy, and men cannot go on digging it up for long; wherefore they first eat garlic and take a draught of neat wine therewith."	IX.VIII.6	<i>Allium sativum</i>	557
Germander	"The leaves are pounded up in olive-oil are used for fractures and wounds and for spreading sores." "The fruit purges bile, and is good also for the eyes; for ulcers in the eye they pound up the leaf in olive-oil before applying it."	IX.IX.5	<i>Teucrium chamaedrys</i>	326
Gold-flower	"And they say the same result follows, if he crowns himself with the flower of gold-flower, sprinkling it with unguent from a vessel of unfired gold. Men use it in wine against the bites of serpents, and to make a plaster for burns after burning it and mixing the ashes with honey."	IX.XIX.2	<i>Helichrysum siculum</i>	297
Golden thistle	"Cause mental derangement...of this Pandeios the sculptor ate, and went mad while he was working in the temple."	IX.XIII.4	<i>Scolymus hispanicus</i>	31
Hartwort	"An Arcadian drug"	IX.XV.5	<i>Tordylium officinale</i>	7
Hemlock	"In most 'roots' the juice thus extracted is less powerful than that of the fruit, but in hemlock it is stronger and it causes an easier and speedier death even when administered in a quite small pill; and it is also more effective for other uses." "Thrasya of Mantinea had discovered, as he said, a poison which produces an easy and painless end; he used the juices of hemlock poppy and other such herbs, so compounded as to make a dose of conveniently small size, weighing only somewhat less than a quarter of an ounce. For the effects of this compound there is absolutely no cure..." "	IX.VIII.3; IX.XVI.8-9	<i>Conium maculatum</i>	11

Herakleia poppy	"It has a leaf like soap-wort, with which they bleach linen. The root of this plant purges upwards: and some use it in a posset of mead for epileptics."	IX.XII.5	<i>Silene venosa</i>	127
Horned poppy (dark/black)	"It has the property of purging the belly, and the leaf is used for removing ulcers on sheep's eyes.	IX.XII.3	<i>Glaucium flavum</i> <i>var. serpierii</i>	65
Libanotis (barren)	"The root can purge both upwards and downwards, the upper part being used for the former, that nearer the ground for the latter purpose. Also, if it is put among clothes, it prevents moth.	IX.XI.11	<i>Lecokia cretica</i> [Family: <i>Umbelliferae</i>]	0
Libanotis (fruitful)	"The fruit is called <i>kakhry</i> . The fruit is good for strangury, for the ears, for ulcers on the eye, for ophthalmia, and for producing mil in women." root - "a large stout white root, which smells like frankincense..." "The root is serviceable for sores, and for diseases of women when given in a draught of dry black wine."	IX.XI.10	<i>Lactuca graeca</i>	83
Long pepper (black)	"Both however are heating: wherefore these, as well as frankincense, are used as antidotes for poisoning by hemlock."	IX.XX.1	<i>Piper nigrum</i>	758
Madder	"It has diuretic properties, wherefore it is used for pains in the loins or hip-disease."	IX.XIII.6	<i>Rubia tinctorum</i>	206
Male-fern	"No part but the root is useful and it has a sweet astringent taste. It expels the flat worm."	IX.XX.5	<i>Nephrodium filix-mas</i>	0

Mandrake	"Used with meal for wounds"; roots - "erysipelas when, scraped and steeped in vinegar, and also for gout, for sleeplessness, and for love potions. It is administered in wine or vinegar; they cut little balls of it, as of radishes, and making a string of them hang them up in the smoke over must."	IX.IX.1	<i>Mandragora officinarum</i>	12
Marsh mallow	"They use it for fractures and for coughs in sweet wine, and for sores in olive-oil."	IX.XV.5	<i>Althaea officinalis</i>	12
Meadow saffron	"On the other hand they say that for meadow-saffron the antidote has been found; for that there is another root which counteracts the herb."	IX.XVI.6	<i>Colchicum parnassicum</i>	127
onotheras (oleander)	"Administered in wine makes the temper gentler and more cheerful. It gives off a fragrance like wine."	IX.XIX.1	<i>Nerium oleander</i>	123
Opium poppy	"The famous drug which cures sorrow and passion, so that it causes forgetfulness and indifference to ills."	IX.XV.1	<i>Papaver somniferum</i>	246
Pepper (red)	"Both however are heating: wherefore these, as well as frankincense, are used as antidotes for poisoning by hemlock."	IX.XX.1	<i>Capsicum spp.</i>	189
Polypody	"It purges downwards: and, if one wears it as an amulet, they say that one does not get a polypus."	IX.XIII.6	<i>Polypodium vulgare</i>	97

Rhoias poppy	"It purges downwards"	IX.XII.4	<i>Papaver rhoeas</i>	246
Rupture wort	"The seed of rupture-wort is mixed with the potion given to promote easy vomiting; this plant is a small herb"	IX.X.2	<i>Herniaria glabra</i>	24
Scammony	"Only the juice is useful and no other part."	IX.XX.5	<i>Convulvulus scammonia</i>	51
Scorpion-plant/leopard's bane	"Is like a scorpion and is useful against the sting of that creature and for certain other purposes."	IX.XIII.6	<i>Doronicum cordatum</i>	16
Scythian root/sweet root/Licorice	"It is useful against asthma or a dry cough and in general for troubles in the chest: also, administered in honey, for wounds: also it has the property of quenching thirst, if one holds it in the mouth: wherefore they say that the Scythians, with the help of this and mares' milk cheese can go eleven or twelve days without drinking."	IX.XIII.2	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>	463
Snapdragon	"Snapdragon produces fair fame. The man who anoints himself with this they say wins fair fame. "	IX.XIX.2	<i>Antirrhinum orontium</i>	22

Spurge	"It is mixed with 'mountain cabbage' [to kill pigs]"	IX.XII.1	<i>Euphorbia apios</i>	1246
Strykhnos	"Induces sleep. The 'bark' of the root of this they bruise severely, and it induces sleep."	IX.XI.5	<i>Withania somnifera</i>	206
Strykhnos/thorn-apple	"The kind which produces madness (which some call <i>thryoron</i> and some <i>peritton</i>) has a white hollow root about a cubit long. Of this three twentieths of an ounce in weight is given, if the patient is to become merely sportive and to think himself a fine fellow; twice this dose if he is to go mad outright and have delusions; (and then they say that the juice of centaury is mixed with it); four times the dose is given, if the man is to be killed."	IX.XI.6	<i>Datura stramonium</i>	183
Sulphurwort	"The root of sulpher-wort is also heating, wherefore they make of it an ointment to produce a sweat, as with other things so used. This root is also given for the spleen: but neither its seed nor its juice is of use: it grows in Arcadia.	IX.XV.5	<i>Peucedanum officinale</i>	191
Thapisa	"The root of <i>thapsia</i> has emetic properties: and, if one retains it, it purges both upwards and downwards. It is also able to remove bruises: and it restores other contusions to a pale colour. Its juice is stronger and purges both upwards and downwards: the seed is not used. The cattle of the country do not touch it, but imported cattle feed on it and perish of diarrhea."	IX.XX.3	<i>Thapsia garganica</i>	95

Tithymallos	"And the tithymallos (spurge) of which <i>hippophaes</i> is made."	IX.XV.6	<i>Euphorbia peplus</i>	1246
Tithymallos (male)	"Of this they collect the juice at the time of vintage, and, after preparing it, use it as occasion demands; and it purges chiefly downwards."	IX.XI.8	<i>Euphorbia sibthorpii</i>	1246
Tithymallos (myrtle-like)	"The fruit of it is called a 'nut'. They gather it when the barley is ripening and dry it and clean it; (it is the actual fruit which they clean); they wash it in water and, after drying it again, give it in a draught mixing with it two parts of 'black poppy'; and the whole dose amounts to about an eighth of a pint. It purges phlegm downwards. If they administer the 'nut' itself, they first pound it up in sweet wine, or give it in parched sesame to bite up.	IX.XI.9	<i>Euphorbia myrsinites</i>	1246
Tithymallos (sea-spurge)	"It is gathered when the grape is just turning, and the dried fruit is given in a draught, the dose being the twenty-fourth part of a pint."	IX.XI.7	<i>Euphorbia paralias</i>	1246
Tripolion	"Thus they say that <i>tripolion</i> according to Hesiod and Musaeus is useful for every good purpose, wherefore they dig it up by night, camping on the spot."	IX.XIX.2	<i>Aster tripolium</i>	238
Unnamed "Ethiopian" root	"Ethiopia there is a certain deadly root with which they smear their arrows."	IX.XV.2	<i>Valeriana dioscoridis</i>	232

Unnamed root	"Fatal effects, as that which grows near the mines in the fields of Thrace: this however is inoffensive and quite sweet to the taste, and the death which it causes is easy and like falling asleep."	IX.XIII.4	?	?
White hellebore	"The white eaten by sheep, and from this circumstance the virtue of the plant was first observed, since it purges them; it is at its prime in autumn."	IX.XI.1-4	<i>Veratrum album</i>	160
Wild cabbage [raddish]/kerais	?	IX.XV.5	<i>Raphanus raphanistrum</i>	91
Wild cucumber/"squirting cucumber"	"Is used for white leprosy and for mange in sheep"; "Makes the drug called 'the driver'" - "it effects a thorough purge upwards"	IX.IX.4	<i>Ecballium elaterium</i>	16
Wild lettuce	"The collection of juices is made either from the stalks, as with <i>tithymallos</i> , wild lettuce, and the majority of plants..."	IX.VIII.2	<i>Lactuca scariola</i>	83
Wild vine' (bryony)	"The root of 'wild vine' (bryony) is also heating and pungent: wherefore it is useful as a depilatory and to remove freckles: and the fruit is used for smoothing hides."	IX.XX.2	<i>Bryonia cretica</i>	94

<p>Wolf's bane</p>	<p>"In its root resides its deadly property, whereas they say that the leaf and the fruit produce no effects. Neither sheep nor any other animals eat it. In order to be effective it is said that it must be compounded in a certain manner, and that not everyone can do this: and so that physicians, not knowing how to compound it, use it as a septic and for other purposes: and that, if drunk mixed in wine or a honey-posset, it produces no sensation: but that it be so compounded as to prove fatal at a certain moment which may be in two, three, or six months, or in a year, or even in two years: and that the longer the time the more painful the death, since the body then wastes away, while, if it acts at once, death is quite painless. And it is said that no antidote which can counteract it has been discovered, like the natural antidotes to other poisonous herbs of which we are told: though the country-folk can sometimes save a man with honey and wine and such things, only however occasionally and with difficulty."</p>	<p>IX.XVI.4-5</p>	<p><i>Aconitum anthora</i></p>	<p>909</p>
<p>Yellow water-lily/<i>madonais</i></p>	<p>"And it is said that it acts as a styptic if it is pounded up and put on the wound: it is also serviceable in the form of a draught for dysentery."</p>	<p>IX.XIII.1</p>	<p><i>Nuphar luteum</i></p>	<p>69</p>
<p>Iris-perfume</p>	<p>"On the other hand this perfume acts as a laxative on the bowels because of its heating quality and because it astringes the passages leading to the bladder: for, when these are closed, the liquid collects in the bowels."</p>	<p><i>On Odours</i>, VIII.1</p>	<p>Unidentifiable</p>	<p>Unknown</p>
<p><i>Megaleion</i></p>	<p>"<i>Megaleion</i> is believed to relieve the inflammation caused by any wound"</p>	<p><i>On Odours</i>, VIII.1</p>	<p>Unidentifiable</p>	<p>Unknown</p>

Rose-perfume	"And rose-perfume to be excellent for the ears."	<i>On Odours,</i> VIII.1	Unidentifiable	Unknown
---------------------	--	-----------------------------	----------------	---------

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bakker, Egbert J., ed. *Companion to the Ancient Greek Language*. (Hoboken: Wiley-Blackwell, 2010).

Bennett, B.C. "Doctrine of Signatures: An Explanation of Medicinal Plant Discovery or Dissemination of Knowledge?" *Economic Botany* 61, (2007): 246-255.

Bers, V., "Kunstprosa: Philosophy, History, Oratory," In *Companion to the Ancient Greek Language*. ed. Bakker, Egbert J. (Hoboken: Wiley-Blackwell, 2010).

Bevan-Jones, R. *Poisonous Plants: A Cultural and Social History*. (Oxford: Windgather Press, 2009).

Bonani, G. et al. "AMS ¹⁴C Age Determination of Tissue, Bone, and Grass Samples from the Ötztal Ice Man." *Radiocarbon* 36(2), (1994).

Cooper, W. *Challenges of the Muslim World: Present, Future and Past*. (UK: Emerald Group Publishing Limited, 2008).

Diogenes Laertius, *Lives of Eminent Philosophers*. Translation by R.D. Hicks, The Loeb Classical Library. (Cambridge: The Harvard University Press, 1972).

Egerton, Frank N., *History of plant science*. (Ipswich: Salem Press Encyclopedia of Science, 2015).

Falagas, M. et al. "Arab science in the golden age (750-1258 C.E.) and today". *FASEB* 20, (2006): 1581-1584.

Gupta, M. "Pharmacological Properties and Traditional Therapeutic Uses of Important Indian Spices: A Review." *International Journal of Food Properties* 13, (2010), 1092-1116.

Hacker, M., Messer II, W., Bachmann, K. *Pharmacology: Principles and Practice*. (USA: Elsevier, 2009),

Heinrich, M., Barnes, J., Gibbons, S., Williamson, E. *Fundamentals of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry* (Churchill Livingstone: Elsevier Limited 2003).

Levey, M. *Early Arabic Pharmacology: An Introduction Based on Ancient and Medieval Sources*. (Leiden: E.J. Brill, 1973).

Lewis, W. H., Elvin-Lewis, M. P. F. *Medical Botany*. (New York: John Wiley and Sons, 2007).

Locher, A. "The Structure of Pliny the Elder's Natural History." In *Science in the Early Roman Empire: Pliny the Elder, his Sources and Influences*, ed. Roger French and Frank Greenway (Kent: Biddles Ltd, 1986), 20-25.

Michael D. Parkins. "Pharmacological Practices of Ancient Egypt." Presentation at the Proceedings of the 10th Annual History of Medicine Days, University of Calgary, Calgary, AB, Canada, March 23-24, 2001.

Miller, J.I., *The Spice Trade of the Roman Empire* (London: Oxford University Press, 1969)

O'Sullivan, Lara. "The Law of Sophocles and the Beginnings of Permanent Philosophical Schools in Athens". *Testimonia Homerica* 145, (2002): 251-262.

Pagel, W. *Paracelsus: An Introduction to Philosophical Medicine in the Era of the Renaissance*. (Basel: S.Karger AG, 1982).

Pliny the Elder. *Loeb Classical Library: The Natural History*. H. Rackham, Trans. (Harvard: Harvard University Press, 1942).

Powell, M. "Drug and Pharmaceuticals in Ancient Mesopotamia." ed. Irene & Walter Jacob. *The Healing Past: Pharmaceuticals in the Biblical and Rabbinic World*. (Leiden: E.J. Brill, 1993).

Prioreschi, P., *A History of Medicine: Vol. III - Roman Medicine* (Omaha: Horatius Press, 1998).

Reynolds, J. "The Elder Pliny and his Times." In *Science in the Early Roman Empire: Pliny the Elder, his Sources and Influences*, ed. Roger French and Frank Greenway (Kent: Biddles Ltd, 1986), 1-10.

Riddle, J.M. *Contraception and Abortion from the Ancient World to the Renaissance*. (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1994).

Scarborough, John. "Drugs and Drug Lore in the Time of Theophrastus: Folklore, Magic, Botany, Philosophy, and the Rootcutters". *Acta* 49, (2006).

Scarborough, J. "Early Byzantine Pharmacology." *Dumbarton Oaks Papers Symposium on Byzantine Medicine*, 38 (1984).

Scarborough, John. "Theophrastus on Herbals and Herbal Remedies". *Journal of the History of Biology* 11, (1978): 353-385.

Seelig, M.G. *Medicine: An Historical Outline*. (Baltimore: The Williams and Wilkins Company, 1931).

Scurlock, J. *Sourcebook for Ancient Mesopotamian Medicine*. (Atlanta: SBL Press, 2014).

Stannard, J. 'Medicinal plants and folk remedies in Pliny, *Historia Naturalis*.' *History and Philosophy of the Life Sciences* 4, (1982).

Theophrastus, *De Causis Plantarum*. Translation by Benedict Einarson and George K.K. Link, The Loeb Classical Library, The Harvard University Press, 1976.

Theophrastus, *Enquiry into Plants*. Translation by Sir Arthur Hort, The Loeb Classical Library, Cambridge, The Harvard University Press, 1946.

Tirinilli, B. et al. "Essential Oil Composition of *Tordylium apulum* L. from Italy." *Journal of Essential Oil Research* 18(1), (2006).

Warmington, E.H., *The Commerce between the Roman Empire and India*, 2nd ed. (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1974).

Ed. Wear, A., French, R.K., Lonie, I.M. *The Medical Renaissance of the Sixteenth Century*. (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1985).